

Deliverable 2.1

Task 2.1 Community Governance Audit

Version 1.0

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Executive Summary

This deliverable focused on a critical evaluation of the governance environment specific to the six Transition Coastal Labs (TCL). The primary objective of *EmpowerUs* is to understand the nature of power in marine environments and to better position local communities to exercise greater control over their natural, social and economic development. Mapping the challenges that each area faces; how the policy network is structured; how power in various forms is enacted; what discourses dominate; and how place is organised are all essential in building more effective local responses in each Lab.

The methodology involved the development of a *workbook* with Lab partners to map out: Understanding the Community; Stakeholder Mapping; Evaluating Policy Discourses; Mapping Structures; and Understanding Policy Processes. Data gathering involved the development of a policy document library; critical analysis of key programmes impacting on the Lab; and 134 in-depth interviews with key stakeholders across the public, private and community sectors in the six TCLs.

Each Lab report sets out local challenges, especially for nature and Nature Based Solutions (NBS); how the community has been impacted by economic change; the role and potential of policy to address these complex challenges; and gives an insight into the personality of each TCL and the potential for local action. However, there are a number of common strands across the Labs that are rooted in economic restructuring that impacts on labour and housing markets, the nature of investment and the use and development of nature, the landscape and marine resources. These are not exhaustive, but include:

- Demographic structure and sustainability is a common strand across the Labs in the way in which complex population restructuring brought in migrant workers from different cultural, linguistic, religious and ethnic backgrounds; pressures in sustaining services; outmigration of young and better-educated people; and ageing, accelerated by retirement migration.
- Housing access and affordability and especially the lack of social and affordable options for the indigenous community.
- Labour market restructuring reflected in significant shifts in the economy of island and coastal communities from traditional primary industries in fishing and farming to more advanced circuits of (increasingly global) production in services, tourism and food processing.
- Structural vulnerability as many peripheral coastal communities and islands are still reliant on a single economic sector or even an individual employer. Diversifying the industrial base is critical but this is often presented to many coastal communities as a rationale for intensive and damaging forms of growth.
- Peripherality affects most Labs, characterised by remoteness, even isolation, which is part of their attraction, but as services increasingly centralise (in both the private and the public sector), connectivity has become a more significant barrier to local development.
- Environmental shocks have intensified brought about by climate change including heat island effects, pollution discharge, sea level rises, eutrophication and algae cover, warmer waters and shorter ice cover periods.

However, each Lab community has also identified significant assets, especially *nature*, on which inclusive and balanced forms of development can be based. This include traditional industries in salt, seaweed and fishing; scenery and natural beauty; a rich cultural heritage; as well as a capacity to connect with the growth economy and innovation, using technology, to reduce the frictional effects of distance.

It is also important to understand what we mean by power and how it is politically transmitted in coastal environments. The analysis of policy documents and the programme of in-depth interviews identified multiple sources, types, significance and effects of power routines in the Lab areas. These include:

- Pluralist politics which still dominate liberal democratic forms of voting for elected representatives who can challenge, advocate and deliver change in and for (as well as against) Lab communities.
- Market rational power evidenced by blue growth regimes in favour of traditional, local and embedded economies and labour market structures.
- Clientist and corporatist forms of policy that remove key decision-making processes from the local level, community access and an ability to challenge.
- Techno-rational and bureaucratic decision making that privileges rules-bound, professionally dominated and rational policy processes, that often exclude or limit access to NGOs and community organisations.
- Semi-judicial, including legal arenas involving planning approvals and appeals, regulatory instruments and land use designations that can serve to protect landscapes and natural resources as well as enable economic development.
- Local people have agency and special committees, decentred governance arrangements and open protest has and can, exercise influence over policy, resist development and build coalitions to effect change.

The concern across Labs is that particular forms of blue growth in tourism, energy, resource extraction, corporate fishing and aquaculture have disembedded the economy from communities, landscapes as commons, traditions and natural resources. Such economies are extractive and impact (as noted) on: demographic structures (especially migration); affordability and access to the housing market; environmental damage; and the displacement of traditional small-scale businesses with corporate (even global) investor interests.

The analysis also focused on *how* policy is structured, the narratives that are used to frame the coast and the rationale for intervention as well as how community and place is articulated in a range of policy and programme narratives:

- New infrastructure (roads, ports, sea defences) and the need to modernise the Lab area to be more competitive and innovative, underpin blue-growth regimes and ready places for particular types of investment and property development. It is *logical*, rational and even desirable to pursue such strategies.
- Linked to this is the way in which a number (not all) Labs are problematized. There is a rhetoric of *pathos* in the decline and terminal decay of coastal economies. Catastrophizing the viability of places also fronts blue growth interests, speculative development and a dependence on outsiders (investors) to save islands and salvage remote communities.
- However, there are also practices, discourses and ethics (*ethos*) that express different forms of value, the importance of community-based ownership and an attitude to nature and local resources not informed by growth or profit. There is potential in social value, collective ownership and the curative *use value* of the sea that are a corrective to blue growth.

Understanding how policy is structured and how Lab communities can be imagined (in need of help, unemployed potential, resources for extraction and so on) needs to be understood at the local level. When the TCLs look at scale, replication and adaptation of pilot interventions, how they relate to these processes, discourses and organisational structures will be essential.

It is not just the type of policy or the relative (economic, political, or regulatory) power that stakeholders possess but where in the institutional structure they are located and how much access communities have to different decision-making arenas. The need to understand and negotiate government and governance structures is critical:

- Many arenas where decisions about the coast are taken, such as how investors are incentivised or secure access to coastal locations, are made well away from community scrutiny, especially where global property interests are active.
- National policy sees the coast as a development opportunity with economic rather than social or sustainability objectives dominating centralised decision-making cultures.
- As we go down the policy hierarchy, place, community and sustainability become more prominent but resource allocation, investment decisions and the regulatory environment already structure what is possible at the municipal level.
- Municipalities are often weak, have limited powers or are being amalgamated, taking decision making access away from localised communities.
- The re-location authority (licensing, planning guidance, funding programmes, regulatory instruments) to the regional level, also removes or rescales fundamental aspects of decision making away from coastal communities.
- However, the hyperlocal is an important site of organisation, resistance (especially to environmental damage) and mobilisation around local campaigns, using grassroots activism, social media and online communities and to use *assets* to create a more inclusive model of community empowerment.

The deliverable and the resources that sit behind it, will support the development of the pilots: how they are implemented; who needs to be involved (and how we understand where they fit and how they act); spaces and opportunities for community action; and evaluating the impact of the pilot on the capacity of local people to exercise greater control over their environments, place and quality of life.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable sets out the results of an extensive baseline analysis of the policy, political, governance and actor structure in the six Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs). It involves a standardised (as far as practicable) approach to mapping users of the sea, the policy regime affecting the development of each area and compiles resources in the form of stakeholder contacts; policy and research papers; and transcripts that will be relevant across work packages and the development of the pilot.

1.1 Objectives

The scope and content of the report is guided by four key objectives:

1. To define the stakeholders involved in the development of the Lab areas;
2. To explore the policy processes and discourses within and between the six TCLs;
3. To define the governance structures, scalar relations and organisation of local development across the case sites; and
4. To set out the cross-cutting themes on governance, policy and actor networks in the TCLs.

1.2 Standardized workbook approach

A standardised methodology was developed and prepared as a workbook to be used across Lab areas. This was outlined and discussed in the kick-off meeting and refined and developed after discussions with each Lab area and the partner organisations in particular. Individual meetings with the Labs guided delivery and clarified the meaning and standardisation of key terms and concepts. An extract from the workbook is set out which offers guidance, explanations, questions and methods relevant to the critical stages of task 2.1. This looked at the following aspects of the work: Using the Workbook; Stage 1 Understanding the Community; Stage 2 Stakeholder Mapping; Stage 3 Evaluating Policy Discourses; Stage 4 Mapping Structures; Stage 5 Understanding Policy Processes; How to Report Your Analysis

Figure 1 Extract from the workbook on delivering Task 2.1

Data gathering, therefore, consisted of a number of common tasks in each area, including:

- A desk-based study of national, regional, and local policies, plans, programmes, and relevant legislation. The scope also involved regulatory processes, including Environmental and Strategic Environmental Planning assessments, zoning regulations and planning appeals cases.
- Research studies and evaluations into the economy, labour market structure, population change, community infrastructure and so on.
- The grey literature is important in terms of press and social media reports, campaigning material by users of the sea, such as on depopulation, environmental controversies, and objector protests.
- A series of interviews with representatives from a number of government departments, local government representatives as well as other relevant stakeholders from NGOs, businesses, parents' associations as well as people who live in the area and related users of the sea.
- Different Lab research approaches involved participant observation, especially across community meetings and events as well as several visits to better understand the area and contested sites and related projects within it.

1.3 Stakeholder mapping and discourse analysis

Here, we take stakeholder to mean any person or agency with a material or emotive stake in the use, development or management of the territory (land, sea and air) in a way that impacts on the local community (based on Healey, 2010). As Mitchell et al. (1997) noted, these vary and they each hold a different stock of power, resources and legitimacies. For example, discretionary stakeholders may have little urgency or power and are unlikely to exert much pressure, while dormant stakeholders might have little legitimacy or urgency and are less likely to become heavily involved. Dominant stakeholders have both formal power and legitimacy and could be in the public, private or community sectors. Here, each stakeholder was positioned as a primary, secondary or tertiary actor and related to this, the influence they held in decision making. The mapping process took a pragmatic approach to the identification of stakeholders operating at each level of the policy hierarchy, but attempted to understand the nature of the power they hold, especially via the semi-structured interviews. This helped to build the stakeholder map and each Lab now has an inventory that acts as a resource throughout the design, delivery and evaluation of the pilot programme. The image below is an extract from the Finnish Lab area.

Stakeholder (other)	Name	Organization, network or interest	Brief summary of their stake or agenda	Primary stakeholder		Secondary stakeholder		Tertiary stakeholder	
				Decision leader	Influence decision-maker	Active decision-maker	Connected to decision-maker	No power	
1		Private/People of influence:	Engagement in environmental and community care - private donation started the Baltic sea		x				
2		Private/People of influence:	Radda Lumparn (NGO), "Save the Lumparn water", politician, sustainability, environment, Jomala, socialdemocrat, ex ministre 2011-15	x					
3		Private/People of influence:	Business man/board member and local initiator, chair on several boards, professional fisheries		x				
4	Högskolan på Åland	Education&Research	University level education			x			
5	Ålands lyceum	Education	Secondary education						x
6	Grundskolan Åland	Education	Compulsory education 1-9 grade						x
7	Yrkesgymnasiet	Education	Vocational education - no fisheries						x
8	Åbo Akademi, Husö Biologiska	Education&Research	Research facility, external stakeholder with international visitors				x		
9	Ålands Jakt- och Fiskemuseum	Museum, tradition, historical	Local hunting and fishing museum						x
10	Sjökvartret Mariehamn	Museum, tradition, historical	Traditional seafarers' quarters						x
Intergovernmental									
1	Government of Finland- Representative for Åland		Minister of Åland	x					
2	EU representative DG Mare		DG Mare, Åland representative	x					
3	MP EU		Finland, SFP liberal party	x					
Public National (Åland)									
Self-governing province of the Åland Islands									
1	Åland Island government - Ålands landskapsregering	Government	Åland is an autonomous region of Finland. The government is led by a Lantråd, the premier minister of Åland, who is elected by the Lanting, the parliament of Åland.	x					
		Administration		x					
2		Åland council			x				
3		Fisheries agency	Head of the bureau			x			
4		Environmental agency	Head of the bureau				x		
5		Forest/hunting agency	Head of the bureau					x	
Public Regional									

Figure 2 Stakeholder map sample from the Åland TCL (Note: Personal information has been redacted)

The stakeholder map sets the context for the document search and the development of a Policy Library for each Lab. These contained copies of the key programmes, plans and research in each case. The profile also enabled the identification of in-depth interview subjects and Annex I sets out the questionnaire that was used across the six TCLs. The Lab descriptions in this report explain the nature and number of the interviews carried out in each case. In total, 134 stakeholder interviews were conducted across Lab area although these vary in size, the complexity of their governance environment and actor networks. The profile of respondents is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Profile of stakeholder interviews

There is a considerable conceptual and methodological literature on policy routines and how to unpack their meaning and an explanation of Discourse Analysis available from Eklipse. Our approach is to explore sites of argumentation and how these are justified (in text, interviews, specific cases in each Lab) and positioning effects or how a stakeholder (institutions, key actor or loose network) engage in interplay with other interests. This sets a context for an analysis of practices in particular cases of argumentation and how they might connect with other arguments, use of words and narratives and where they confront or challenge competing discourses. The analysis draws out discursive structures, rhetorical devices and sites of production of different (competing and overlapping) narratives about the coast, development and hidden routines of power and empowerment.

The next six sections describe the results of the research across each Lab area, in a consistent way as far as is practicable. This provides a context for the development of cross-cutting themes linked to power, empowerment, and the potential of each Lab to create a pilot that addresses, in part, the issues raised in the mapping process. The final section (4) sets out how it is intended that the report and the resources created including the stakeholder map, policy library and interview transcripts will be usable across the research programme and work packages.

2. Reports from Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs)

2.1 TCL Report: Bulgaria

By Anna Antonova

2.1.1 Introduction

Atanasovsko Lake is a coastal lagoon located north of the city of Burgas. It is a part of the Burgas lakes complex, which is one of the three most significant wetland complexes for congregations of waterfowl along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast. The region of Atanasovsko Lake currently supports a total of 334 bird species. The lake is a Natura 2000 site (Special Protected Area and Site of Community Interest) with vital ecosystem functions, including as a key nesting and feeding habitat for birds on the Via Pontica migratory route. Parts of the lake are used for salt-making by traditional salt extraction techniques. Ocean literacy and civic engagement projects previously in place have shown that the lake can serve as a benchmark for nature conservation, local development, and service development.

Summary of research participants by sector:

Stakeholder sector	Number
Community	4
Voluntary sector – NGOs	2
Public	6
Private	4
Other	2

2.1.2 Understanding the community; mapping structures & decision-making

The Bulgarian Black Sea coast and Burgas municipality

The city of Burgas, Bulgaria’s fourth largest at ca. 200,000 citizens (NSI, 2021), is administered by the municipality of Burgas and also serves as the administrative seat for the region of Burgas—Bulgaria’s largest single region in terms of territory, covering the entire southern half of the Bulgarian coastline. Whereas municipalities are locally elected, regional governors are appointed by the central government to coordinate with individual municipalities and represent national priorities (i.e., developing road infrastructure) at the local and regional levels. Responsibilities for the regional application of national (and EU) environment and water-basin management policies similarly fall to regional institutions, respectively the Regional Inspectorate for Environment and Waters Burgas and the Black Sea Basin Directorate in Varna (both under the purview of the Ministry of the Environment and Waters).

While until the mid-20th century the coastal economy of the southern Bulgarian Black Sea coast was dominated by salt making (Andreev & Grozdanova, 1982), over the second half of the century tourism became an important economic driver for both region and country. Today, tourism is the coastline’s foremost industry, as well as a major source of income nationally, amounting to roughly 18.9% of Bulgaria’s GDP in 2022 (NSI, 2023). In Burgas, the Lukoil Neftohim Burgas oil refinery also plays a vital role as a local employer (Burgas Regional Administration, n.d.; Nikolov, 2021). A need to diversify the economy and revitalize the city’s image has been clearly identified as a priority in local governance discourses (see next section).

Figure 4 Map of the Bulgarian TCL Area. (From <http://plepe.at/45>).

Although nearly 80% of the Burgas region population identifies as ethnically Bulgarian (Burgas Regional Administration, 2021), migration has had and continues to have an important impact on the coastline. Most current communities were originally migrants established after the Balkan Wars in the 1930s (Shterionov, 1996); in recent years, the Black Sea coastline and the Burgas region and municipality in particular have found themselves at the crossroads of both the southern and the Ukrainian refugee waves (Interview 1, 2023); but the largest concern expressed by many over the course of the fieldwork period is the *outmigration* particularly of young and middle-class people. This impacts the social fabric of the coastline substantially, both in terms of citizen involvement (Interview 6, 2023; Interview 12, 2023) and in terms of employment. In interviews, institutions ranging from the national to the local level consistently expressed an issue with acquiring or retaining human resources (Interview 1, 2023; Interview 4, 2023; Interview 8, 2023; Interview 10, 2023); while conversations with industry showed that this scarcity extends not only to highly-qualified workers, but also to laborers, who thanks to the EU market have better paid seasonal opportunities abroad (Interview 11, 2023). One participant, borrowing the ecological term, referred to the “functional extinction” of young and active middle-class people in Bulgaria more generally and on the coastline specifically (Interview 6, 2023).

2.1.3 Governance structure & key issues

Centralization & Bulgaria’s ongoing (2021-) political instability

Bulgaria’s governance structure is highly centralized, with policies like regional development plans, environmental governance, regional infrastructure, etc., dependent on national policy through either

national or regional institutions. Moreover, many of the most profitable taxes (including VAT, income taxes, and corporate taxes) are centrally collected at the national level, then reallocated via national budget planning to municipal budgets (Ministry of Finance, n.d.; Interview 1, 2023). Accordingly, the ongoing political instability (April 2nd, 2023, marked the 5th elections in Bulgaria in two years; a 6th round is likely to take place in the fall – see e.g. Bechev, 2023) has a direct effect on regional and municipal policy. In Burgas’ case, for example, the municipality developed its PIRO and waste disposal plans on time in order to comply with EU priorities and timelines, while national governance has lagged—resulting in retroactive adapting of Burgas’ published plans in order to comply with national planning (Interview 1, 2023). This issue impacts human resources, as well: salaries in both the municipality and in the region of Burgas are insufficient for retaining environmental (and other) experts long-term (Interview 1, 2023; Interview 10, 2023) but offering higher salaries requires an updated national budget, which is locked up in the current political instability (Interview 1, 2023).

At the local level, top-down approaches to governance are similarly pronounced. Several participants indicated a tendency for Burgas municipality to “adopt” - or, as some implied, take over and monopolize - successful private entrepreneurial initiatives or ideas and implement them as municipal projects, often at the expense of local communities. In one example, a local entrepreneur’s recreational fishing tourist catamaran was later outcompeted by the municipality’s own vessel, which had the advantage of free municipal berths at the seaport, priority berthing at St. Anastasia Island, and subsidized fuel usage (Interview 14, 2023). Another participant described the development of the Chengene skele fishing museum, which he himself had proposed in a meeting as a functional open-air museum directly involving local fishermen (thereby also resolving long-standing permitting issues in their village), but which the municipality instead implemented as a separate museum complex built to one side of the fishing village (Interview 6, 2023). Finally, other participants separately claimed that the municipality - and neighboring municipalities - had developed top-down initiatives to replicate and replace existing bottom-up initiatives in an attempt to support dominant political agendas (Interview 9, 2023; Interview 12, 2023). Successful citizen initiatives, in this sense, are not always meaningfully integrated into the governance process through robust bottom-up mechanisms. Indeed, participants can feel that citizen initiatives and volunteers’ work are not valued on a societal level (Interview 12, 2023).

Future planning

According to both PIRO Burgas and officials involved with its planning, Burgas sees its future development as an identity transformation “from a postsocialist and depressive to an innovative and modern model of urban development” (PIRO Burgas, 2021, p. 253). This transformation is grounded in several key areas: as an IT remote-hub city (PIRO Burgas, 2021; Interview 12, 2023); as a “blue growth center” (PIRO Burgas, 2021, p. 268; Interview 10, 2023) and industrial center through the adaptation of existing industrial infrastructure to modern corporation needs (Interview 12, 2023); and as a large tourism destination beyond the currently observable seasonality patterns, including through an emphasis on cultural and medical tourism (Interview 12, 2023; Interview 7, 2023). As part of this, the municipality plans on further expanding infrastructure, including a planned Black Sea Highway project set to bridge over the Vaya lake to the south of Burgas and skirt the Atansovsko lake to the north of Burgas (Burgas Land Use Plan, 2023).

Climate change does represent an important part of both the PIRO and Burgas’ planning discourses more generally. Burgas’ location between the Burgas Bay of the Black Sea and the three lakes (Atanasovsko, Vaya, and Mandra) transforms it into a “heat island,” exposing it to changing rain patterns of long drought periods and intensified rainfall events leading to flooding; September 2022 saw a hurricane—something atypical for Bulgaria—hitting the city (Interview 1, 2023; Interview 3, 2023; BNT, 2022). While the Municipality of Burgas has invested in an advanced early-warning system for flooding, this covers only the municipality’s territory, limiting the reach of its monitoring; national

policy that would enable wider observations at the regional level is still lagging behind (Interview 3, 2023).

Atanasovsko lake

Against this context, the Atanasovsko lake is seen to have an important potential role as an alternative model for development, akin to definitions by Gibson-Graham and Miller of ecological economic livelihoods (2015; Interview 2, 2023; Interview 13, 2023). Salt production in the lake helps maintain an ecosystem protected under both national and Natura 2000 legislation; the lake along with its salt production has become an alternative tourist attraction due to its distinctive red-colored pools in summer, the presence of many bird species including an increased presence of flamingos in recent years (“from 3 to 3,000 individuals” (Interview 14, 2023)), and the attraction of the curative mood pools that are the by-product of salt production. NGOs, including and especially the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation and the Bulgarian Society for the Protection of Birds, have been actively involved in promoting the lake and its place in both city life (as a park appending Burgas) and in the local tourist landscape. Promotion materials demonstrate that the Burgas municipality has also recognized the value of the lake (and its flamingos) for its tourism marketing (*Go to Burgas*, 2023).

The lake’s protected area is listed under national legislation as a “maintained” protected area (allowing for salt extraction) (Michev et al., 2003), under EU Natura 2000 legislation as a protected site under the Birds *and* Habitats Directives, and under international legislation as a Ramsar site. Within the lake and the protected area, land is nationally owned; the lake is abutted by municipally owned land to the north, northeast, northwest, and east, as well as by a small amount of privately-owned land to the north and west (Michev et al., 2003; Interview 5, 2023). Within the lake, however, all salt-making infrastructure (pumping stations, dykes, storage buildings and facilities) is privately owned and maintained by “Chernomorski solnitsi JSC” in accordance with a 2000 privatization contract (Interview 5, 2023); the only exception is the lake bypass channel, which has been owned by the municipality since 2020.

The protected area’s habitat is dependent on the continuation of the salt-making process, making this Bulgaria’s only protected area so strongly dependent on private activity (Interview 5, 2023). The precise extent to which the privatization contract specified the private owner’s responsibilities towards the maintenance of the protected area and its biodiversity is currently not publicly known and is in the process of being clarified by the Ministry of the Environment and Water (Interview 5, 2023). At the same time, there have been multiple financial pressures on the salt producer, particularly ones associated with the coastline’s further development. Burgas’ growing urbanization and new road infrastructure around the lake (nicknamed “Sunny Beach Highway”) increase the outflow into the bypass channel and respectively the salt producer’s pumping costs; these costs are set to grow even further with future road infrastructure planned around the lake (Interview 11, 2023; Burgas Land Use Plan, 2023). Should salt production become unprofitable for the salt producer, the cessation of activities in the lake would negatively impact the protected area, exposing the Ministry of the Environment to potential breach of its responsibilities towards the EU under Natura 2000 legislation (Interview 5, 2023; Interview 11, 2023). This is exacerbated by the fact that a number of EU-funded LIFE projects (one ongoing) have supported the ecosystem’s restoration and further preservation (LIFE08 NAT/BG/000277; LIFE11 NAT/BG/000362; LIFE17 NAT/BG/000558), underlining the lake’s perceived high value at a European level.

2.1.4 Evaluating policy discourses and crosscutting issues in the Lab

A commonly raised discourse in the context is that of unsustainable development, particularly the longstanding over-emphasis on tourism with profits/benefits not distributed evenly across community (as especially the Q sorts have captured). Overinvestment in seasonally occupied tourism-related construction along the southern coastline has started to result in the permanent closure of large investment properties in the region and means that locals (especially those outside of Burgas city)

now face simultaneously a dependency on the tourist industry and diminishing returns for investing in it (Gencheva, 2022; Interview 9, 2023).

Tensions between economic growth and environmental protection

For many non-institutional participants, planning in the municipality and in the region has included important oversights where it comes to diversifying the economy and taking the environment seriously. For instance, the planned infrastructural expansions are expected to place further environmental pressure on the lakes and on salt production (Interview 6, 2023; Interview 11, 2023). Already completed infrastructural projects have either directly negatively impacted the environment as in the case of the Pomorie lake and Atanasovsko lake (Interview 9, 2023; Life for Pomorie, 2023; Interview 11, 2023) or have obstructed access to the environment as in the case of the Vaya lake, where new roads make bird watching from the city impossible (Interview 6, 2023). Meanwhile, proposals to develop the city as a green ecotourist destination and/or as sports capital through the completion of a circular cycling infrastructure were not incorporated into the PIRO, with new road developments actually obstructing possible cycle pathways (Interview 12, 2023). In a similar vein, although blue growth was cited in the PIRO and by institutional participants as an important priority for the city (PIRO Burgas, 2021, p. 268; Interview 10, 2023), other participants noted that in reality “Bulgaria was becoming less and less of a maritime country” (Interview 7, 2023), with shipping of both people and goods declining, stricter restrictions being placed on fishermen, and coastal ecosystem-based services being either underutilized or indeed undermined (Interview 2, 2023; Interview 7, 2023; Interview 9, 2023). Several participants spoke of the importance of enabling and better incorporating (in short: empowering) bottom-up initiatives into the local governance (Interview 12, 2023; Interview 16, 2023).

Many institutions and non-institutional participants cited their concern with a lack of financial resources, both in general, but also currently due to the country’s political instability. Some participants spoke of their sense of a lamentable chronic dependency on European funding and thus program/project-oriented thinking dominant across the Bulgarian planning culture, as opposed to what a necessary longer-term view of investment and planning; others went so far as to suggest that policy at least at the local level was entirely driven by what project funding might be available at the moment (Interview 5, 2023; Interview 7, 2023). Among participants not directly in the governance processes, discussions of financial resources often related to an overarching discourse of corruption and government dysfunction (e.g., Interviews 3, 7, 9, 14, 2023), particularly in cases where territories containing key ecosystems ended up being designated as future urbanized plots (see e.g., *Mediapool*, 2023). These discourses communicate an existing distrust towards institutions in the context, as well as ongoing concern among the community for the coastline’s sustainable future.

2.2 TCL Report: Cyprus

By Maria Hadjimichael

2.2.1 Introduction

The Cypriot TCL is comprised with three neighbouring communities which are situated in the Eastern Limassol region, along the south coast of Cyprus: Moni (population: 391), Monagrouli (population: 471), and Pentakomo (population: 644). Though these are coastal communities, there is a poor connection to the sea, as the core of the village and the housing zones are situated at the upper side of a motorway which has been constructed in 1978 and is approximately 3 kilometres away from the coast.

Summary of research participants by sector:

Stakeholder sector	Number
Community	11
Voluntary sector – NGOs	2
Public	5
Private	3
Other	0

2.2.2 Understanding the community

There is a variety of social and ethnic groups living in the Lab Area. The majority of the population are Greek Cypriots, thus part of the main ethnic community living in the Republic of Cyprus (RoC). The village of Pentakomo was a bicomunal village, where both main ethnic communities in Cyprus, Greek and Turkish Cypriots inhabited prior to the 1974 violent division of the island. The 1974 division led to the displacement of the Turkish Cypriots of Pentakomo to the northern part of the island. User rights have been given for many TC properties to GCs who were displaced from the northern part of the island.

The coastal land of the Lab area is primarily a mosaic of public and community-owned land and agricultural land. In terms of coastal development, there is only one coastal restaurant at Ayios Georgios Alamanos in Monagrouli, whilst in Pentakomo, there is the cove known as Governor's Beach towards the eastern end of the community where several restaurants and vacation homes exist. At Governor's Beach, the Kalymnos Camping site hosts approximately 360 mobile / prefabricated homes in which over 500 persons are either living permanently or who visit for vacations. The Kalymnos Camping Site has created another small community shared by an interesting mix of people including Cypriots and non-Cypriots who have found cheap accommodation, as well as Cypriots and non-Cypriots who use it as a holiday home. These homes are owned though not through official title deeds. There is also a significant number of recreational fishers who use the area whilst tourists visit for the famous 'white rocks'.

As this report is being prepared, coastal development in the (coastal) Lab Area is limited to Governor's Beach and Ayios Georgios Alamanos. The rest of the infrastructure includes some heavy industries, including a cement factory, a water and waste treatment facility, sites for building waste, an old power station and quarrying zones. A number of these industries are slowly being abandoned and replaced by new uses with a prime example the replacement of a cement factory at Moni by a luxury multi-purpose development which describes itself as a 'city within a city'. The coastal area has high ecological importance, as it hosts several different types of coastal and marine habitats including sand-dunes, reefs, Posidonia meadows, and sea caves. They are also home to important flora and fauna, including (among others) the endangered plant *Neurada procumbens*, the Mediterranean monk seal *Monachus Monachus*, and the Egyptian fruit bat *Rousettus Aegyptiacus*.

2.2.3 Stakeholder mapping

The lack of local associations created difficulties in identifying appropriate representatives of the different societal actors. Competent authorities identified and interviewed included representatives from the Municipal Council (including the President, where possible), officers from the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment, the Town Planning and Housing Department of the Ministry of Interior and Ministry of Commerce, Energy and Industry. To engage with people who fit different profiles living in the Lab area, there was a targeted attempt (often through the snowball technique) to identify people who would fit within certain groups:

- Members of the Parent’s Association of the area’s primary schools,
- People living on both sides of the motorway,
- Owners of coastal businesses (restaurants and rented accommodation),
- Displaced Greek Cypriots living in the Lab Area.

2.2.4 Evaluating policy discourses

There are various conflicting policy discourses which are themselves linked to conflicting economic and ecological objectives and priorities. These are in essence outcomes of the inherent mismatches between the blue economy and conservation objectives.

Coastline and Ecological Protection

As an EU MS, the RoC is expected to protect its biodiversity according to the Habitats Directive. According to the 2022 European Implementation Review, nature protection is one of the main challenges identified by the European Commission and this relates to how a number of the policy discourses relevant to the Lab Area emerge and sometimes create tensions. The EC has initiated an infringement procedure for the insufficient designation of Special Areas of Conservation in Cyprus but also for the incomplete application of Article 6(3) which requires that Any plan or project that is likely to have a significant effect on a Natura 2000 site must be subject to appropriate assessment. The RoC is yet to ratify the Seventh Protocol to the Barcelona Convention on Integrated Coastal Zone Management in the Mediterranean even though the country is legally obliged to follow it since it has been signed and ratified by the European Union as European law. The RoC however still primarily follows its previous legislative framework called ‘the Foreshore Protection Law’ which has various loopholes in allowing shrinking of the length of the foreshore area and its development.

The coastal plots in the Lab Area are in their majority agricultural land and coastal protection zones. There are also few tourist zones, especially in the area known as Governor’s Beach which is part of the community of Pentakomo. In December 2022, the Department of Town Planning and Housing announced the start of the 1st Phase of the process of revision and modification of the Urban Planning Zones in the countryside, which included the Lab area. The revision aims to modernize the Town Planning Zones so that they can support the modern needs of social, cultural and economic development of the countryside in the context of functional, sustainable, environmental and balanced planning.

In February 2023, the Department of Fisheries and Marine Research (DFMR) announced the designation of a Marine Protected Area in the coastal area known as Ayios Georgios Alamanos in Monagrouli for the protection of the endangered Mediterranean Monk Seal. There is currently a discussion that cuts across different interests and competences around the limits of the Natura2000 area linked to this MPA. The discussion is directly linked to the designation of an aquaculture zone in the marine space adjacent to the area in question. In April 2023, the Department of Forests put forward a suggestion to declare two pieces of coastal land in the Lab Area into forest land. The first includes part of the sand dunes of the Moni area and the second is part of the coastal zone in

Monagrouli which is adjacent to the MPA Ayios Georgios Alamanos. The declaration of these areas to Forest Lands essentially sets the ground for stricter protection of the areas.

Blue Growth Opportunities: The Expansion of Marine Aquaculture

In 2014, the Department of Fisheries and Marine Research published the ‘Long-Term National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture 2014-2020’ through which the creation of two Aquaculture Zones were suggested. Though the location of one of them was to be decided upon, the other would remain in the area of Pentakomo / Moni which was described to be the “natural development for that area” as it hosted 75% of marine aquaculture facilities in the RoC (DFMR, 2014; p.27). Complimentary land-based infrastructure would be required to support the expansion of this Aquaculture Zone as the infrastructure currently used was now part of the Vasilikos Energy Centre which was expanded following the discovery of hydrocarbon reserves in the Exclusive Economic Zone of the RoC in 2011. The proposed location for the new marine aquaculture land and port facilities is in the Pentakomo area (see figure 5 below).

The licensing and the construction of the marine aquaculture facilities in Pentakomo is directly in conflict with the protection of the habitat of the Mediterranean Monk Seal in the coastal and marine area of Monagrouli and Pentakomo. The controversy lies in the proposed boundaries of the Natura2000 site with the main critique being that the responsible authority (which is the DFMR) has shrunk the boundaries to allow for the construction of the specific infrastructure.

Figure 5 Regional map for the fishing and aquaculture sector of the proposed Marine Spatial Plan of the Republic of Cyprus. The proposed land and port marine aquaculture facility is in the black circle.

2.2.5 Mapping structures

The local governance context is shaped by a few institutions and what is interesting to note is that there are no institutions beyond the local governments from the Lab area itself beyond the local church and the church committee which in Pentakomo and Monagrouli also includes a women

association. This is not a peculiarity as the church tends to play an important role in local and national politics and decision-making within the RoC.

Each of the three communities has its own elected community council. Each community council has a president, a vice-president and (usually) 7 members. Even though local administration elections take place every five (5) years, the latest elections took place in 2016 as the elections which had to take place in 2021 were postponed in the light of the local administration reform. The next local administration elections will take place in 2024 and the three community councils will become part of a larger community cluster along with 7 other neighbouring communities.

Other existing local structures such as the Parents' Association for the local primary schools tend to focus on issues that are directly linked with issues at the schools. As in most communities in the RoC, hunters are organised around their associations at a regional and national level whilst the local coffee shops are places male adults of the communities gather. There is no fishers' community in the Lab Area besides recreational fishers who fish from the coastline using a rod or spear-fishers. These recreational fishers are generally not organised in a way that influences decision-making.

Sectors that have economic interests in the Lab Area are more organised and tend to be more recognisable. The 'Limassol Chamber of Commerce & Industry' for example is the relevant business lobby for the Lab Area the aim of which is *"to defend the interests of the business community and promote the economic development of the Limassol district"*. There is also the Cyprus Mariculture Association which given the amplified importance of the marine and coastal space of the Lab area for the sector has a particular interest. Finally, foreign investors appear to be particularly influential through a focus on helping developments flow in. Influence can either be through links with the local or national government, or the Chamber. Foreign investors tend to join forces with local developers who can facilitate navigation of relevant processes and access. There are also more local businesses, particularly coastal fish taverns and restaurants and some rented accommodations who are not particularly organised between them but have access to (at least) the local government.

2.2.6 Decision-making structures

Decision-making structures in the Lab area differ across levels but also across issues. The most accessible decision-making body for people living in the Lab area is the local Community Council. The Lab Area is small and most people have access to the Community Council in order to share their views. Official decisions which lie at the responsibility of the Community Council are made by the elected group. For issues which are considered of great importance for the Community at large, community-wide assemblies are called, such as for example the revisions of the existing planning zones.

Depending on the issue at hand, there are different governance structures aiming to facilitate participation in decision-making. For issues linked to new developments in the area, the Department of Environment is the competent authority to ensure that the participation process is done in accordance with the EU's Environmental Impact Assessment Directive. The Community in which a development falls within its administrative boundaries is invited to attend and submit its views with regards to the development or project. The local authority is usually represented by its President or an individual selected by the local authorities.

It is often argued by the local authorities that their participation tends to be symbolic. E-NGOs also participate in such Committees and depending on the issue at hand, e-NGOs can be on the same or in opposing sides with the local authorities. Litigation against decisions is possible, especially in the context of licensing of projects or developments by the State. Nevertheless, this is an option rarely used by local authorities and NGOs for various reasons including lack of financial or legal knowledge, as well as lack of trust in the legal system.

2.2.7 Crosscutting issues in the Lab

The community within the Lab Area is frustrated by the general lack of development opportunities which have opened up along the coastline. Though there was an expectation for a 'new era' following the licensing of a big multi-purpose development in Moni, the promotion of the area as the main marine aquaculture zone for the RoC, and particularly the possible construction of an industrial marine aquaculture harbor will hamper those expectations. Though the community at the Lab Area sees the existing conflict as a conflict between an industrial use, namely marine aquaculture and a residential / tourist use, the alternative vision of protecting a significant part of the coastline because of its ecological significance is also often seen as an obstacle. Envisioned and planned correctly can facilitate a real green coastal transition which can support the development and wellbeing of these coastal communities.

2.3 TCL Report: Finland

By Kristina Svells, Pekka Salmi, and Viktor Eriksson

2.3.1 Introduction

This report is compiled from document analysis of policy document and programs, and structured interviews with key stakeholders of the TLC community – the fisheries sector, local actors, and authorities in five municipalities on Åland Islands, Finland.

Summary of research participants by sector:

Stakeholder sector	Number
Community	2
Voluntary sector – NGOs	4
Public	7
Private	4
Other	0

2.3.2 Understanding the community

The self-governing province of the Åland Islands lies off the southwest coast of Finland. Åland is an autonomous, demilitarised, Swedish-speaking region of Finland. The autonomous status is laid down in this Autonomy Act and areas wherein the Åland parliament has the competence to legislate are laid down in Art. 18 of the Act of the Autonomy of Åland (1991/1144). All business related to internal affairs fall under the competence of the Åland parliament. The relationship between Åland Islands and EU is regulated in the Åland protocol, thus confirming the special status under international law.

Åland consists of over 6,700 islands (60 populated islands) and almost 90% of the total area is sea. Population 30,344 (2021) (11,742 Mariehamn, 16,547 countryside, and 2,055 archipelago). Over 40% live in the capital, Mariehamn, one of Åland’s 16 municipalities. Ålandic municipalities’ economy are based on the governmental counter balancing system. The government regulates the public economies of the 16 municipalities yearly.

Unemployment rate is low 4,6% (2023 ÅSUB). In 2019, the gross domestic product’s value (current market prices) amounted to 1.3 billion EUR, which constituted 45,000 EUR/capita. Ferry and flight infrastructure connect the Åland Islands with Finland and Sweden and islands are reached by a network of local ferries. In 2019 over 389,000 guest nights (in 2021 344,000 due to Covid) in hotels, guest homes, campsites and holiday villages were accumulated (excluding a significant number of stays in smaller facilities and private cottages). In total there are over 7,590 second homes on Åland (Tilastokeskus, 2022) owned by Ålanders and foreigners, often with an Ålandic family tie and homestead rights.

The TCL Åland covers five municipalities on north-northwest of Åland: Geta, Hammarland, Finström, Saltvik and Eckerö. They are described by the directors as ‘rural municipalities, safe and prosperous’. Eckerö, the most westly situation municipality in Finland is also described as a major tourism municipality.

Figure 6 Map of the Municipalities of the Åland Archipelago

Description of the Åland fisheries sector

Capture fisheries and fish farming are major elements of the commercial fisheries sector in Åland. Although the share in the GDP of Åland was 1,4% 2016 (ÅSUB Rapport 2019), fisheries are of substantive importance in terms of local culture, identity, and economy. Local people in the archipelago often fish (e.g., by gill nets) for household consumption and take part in local fisheries management as water owners. Also, numerous non-local recreational fishers (rod fishers) use the Åland fishing waters. These 'tourist fishers' form an important source of income for local entrepreneurs like fishing guides and accommodation providers.

Commercial fishing in Åland can be categorized as 1) large scale open sea fishing for quota species, 2) small-scale coastal fishing for quota species and 3) small-scale coastal fishing for non-quota species (ÅSUB Rapport 2019). The first group represents trawling for Baltic herring and sprat. The small-scale fishers use mostly gill nets and harvest either Baltic salmon and cod (quota species) or various other (non-quota) species like perch, European whitefish, and pikeperch. The gross value of the landings, taking into account import and export, in the archipelago region amounted 3.847 000 EUR in 2016 (PECH Committee). Like in other Finnish coastal areas, most fishers and vessels are small-scale operators.

TCL Fisheries community

The Åland TCL 'community' consists of the fisheries sector stakeholders (both professional and sports fishers, aquaculture, fish conservationists, water owners and a Fisheries Local Action Group) represented by the following organized associations and NGOs below, in addition also household and recreational fishers. Also, several NGOs and associations without a direct linkage to the fisheries sector can be associated to the broad fisheries sector. These denote environmental and nature conservation/protection, tourism, well-being and education issues.

Dominating enterprises and institutions

There are only a few larger institutions situated within the five municipalities that impact the fisheries community. One dominating public institution is the Åbo Akademi University Husö Biological station in Finström. The station is part of Environmental and Marine Biology (Biosciences) and mainly

conducts aquatic research and teaching. Some terrestrial research is also conducted. One large private enterprise in Eckerö is the Fifax RAS aquaculture plant, an establishment that has locally not been conflict free, due to sewage problems and illness in the production cycle. Fruit production and processing enterprises (apples) are dominating the TCL landscape.

Problem statements and conflicts within the TCL

There are no particular ‘unique’ problem statements within the five municipalities, however, problem statements are perceived to be common for the whole of Åland. Regarding fisheries, one statement that was commonly mentioned for all municipalities was that the seal is a major challenge and hinders development of the fisheries sector. However, the fisheries stakeholders did not emphasise the seal as a major challenge if not directly asked, which may be their interpretation of the seal-problem as self-evident for decades.

The seals are considered the main obstacle for sustainable coastal and archipelago fishing also in Finland and Sweden (Svels et al. 2019). Seals have caused direct and indirect losses for the fishing livelihood e.g. by taking or damaging fish near the gear, breaking the nets and scaring fish away from the fishing grounds. At the same time while the seal problem is a major source of conflict in the Åland fisheries, it is challenging to solve due to the rapid growth of grey seal populations and restrictions in hunting and the ban of trading seal products (Svels et al. 2022). There are, however, new technological innovations for harassing the seals away from the fishing gear. These can also be used for creating seal-free areas (sanctuaries for the fish and fishers) in places where entering of the seals can be closed by the acoustic device in narrow straits. Another fish-eating species and source of conflict is the cormorant which affects the fish stocks and fish behaviour but more rarely, compared to the seal, breaks commercial fishers’ nets or damages the fish. The effects of the cormorants on commercial fishers are difficult to estimate (Svels et al 2019). Unlike the seal, which is not easily seen and is a problem for the commercial fishers, the cormorants are visible, with effects noticed and discussed by wider groups of people, such as second home dwellers, household fishers and sport fishers. Seals and cormorants cause damages also in fish farming.

From the commercial fishers’ perspective, the most tangible problem is that catches decrease. Fishers see how growing populations of seals and cormorants have reduced profitability of the livelihood. Also, environmental changes, like eutrophication of the waters and climate change, are obvious reasons behind the decrease of catches. Fish populations and fishing opportunities are affected by the increase of algae, shorter ice cover periods, warmer waters, and windy weathers. Climate change and eutrophication are even more difficult to mitigate by local measures than the seal and cormorant conflicts.

Fishing- and management rights and fisheries sector agenda

Finnish coastal and inland waters have traditionally been under private ownership and associated with the possession of land. This was codified already in a statute of the year 1766 when Finland was a part of Sweden (Eklund 1994). Also, in the fisheries governance of Åland this basic rule remains: all archipelago waters are in private ownership while the deeper waters are public and managed by Åland government. Åland government also manages its own waters and sells fishing licenses for local commercial and recreational fishers.

Water owners are local people who possess land by the shore, but also organizations can own water areas or their shares. Water owners are permanent inhabitants of Åland since ownership of land and water is restricted by the homestead act of Åland. The ownership entails not only the right to fish (use right) but also a right to make decisions (management right). In the owner-based local management the decision maker is commonly a collective, namely a statutory shareholders’ (fishery) association. It jointly represents the interests of individual owners in fishery matters, but it also has obligation for

providing access to fishing and protecting the fish stocks. The association often uses the fishing license income in stocking fish fingerlings. The villages form a traditional areal scope of the associations.

On Åland there are three structural types of owner-based fisheries management: 1) statutory fishery association system, where, based on their legal ownership, private shareholders jointly manage their (village) water area, 2) waters owned and managed by a sole owner, which can be an individual person or an organization including the Åland Government and 3) joint management of a water area without allotment (Neuman 2007). The first alternative, statutory fishery association system, forms the most important local fisheries management system in the studied municipalities. The water owners - shareholders in the association - enjoy limited fishing rights and a right to take part in decision making. They do not, however, always have any personal interest in fisheries, but many of the active decision makers are typically local household fishers.

The water areas of individual statutory fishery associations are usually very small. In some locations commercial fishers have faced challenges in getting access to wide enough fishing areas (Neuman 2007). To make non-local sport fishers' access more easy wider rod fishing license areas have been developed in some areas jointly by several fishery associations; Eckerö is an example where there is a joint license, Eckerökortet, covering waters of six fisheries associations. While these joint license areas help in their local contexts, many tourist entrepreneurs in other areas of the TCL would still prefer to provide wider fishing areas for their guests. Sport fishers operating in small and fragmented license areas have difficulties in avoiding to cross fishery associations' border lines while fishing. All five municipalities own only little water areas. The municipalities take part in some statutory fishery associations' meetings, yet not actively. The municipalities show low interest in taking part in decision-making regarding the fisheries sector and water owning and they do not incorporate the fisheries sector in their strategical long-term planning.

Development agenda for public, private and fisheries sector

There are five fish farming enterprises on Åland. The TCL embrace two fish farming enterprises, one land-based RAS plant and one water based with two production units. All aquaculture licenses are due to be renewed 2024 and with a new expected water law there might be challenges for the fish farms to renew licenses.

Resources within the fisheries sector

Resources in possession by the fisheries sector are privately owned water and shares in water commons. The 'fish resources' (populations) are not owned by anyone and the fishing waters not owned by fisheries sector, however individual fishers may have the fishing right through water ownership. Resources acquired are buildings (cooling houses, processing, sheds for equipment and boats etc.) and constructions for fishing (wharfs, harbours etc.). Mean of production includes boats, equipment, and tools. Personal resources are skill and labour, of which the last is quickly diminishing since fishing is not an attractive profession on Åland anymore. In the local context 'talko', or local gathering for working without payment for a common local cause, is common. For fisheries' communities the water owners common contribute with conservation of water and spawning areas and support infrastructure.

The Åland Fisheries Local Action Group (FLAG) is a Leader-type organization, funded by EMFAF, for enhancing fisheries community-based local development. The Åland FLAG covers the whole province and its strategic goals include: the environment, knowledge and experiences. Yet, the FLAG organization in Åland – unlike FLAGs in other parts of Finland - only rarely funds projects that are directly relevant for the fisheries livelihoods and is more inclined funding environmental and fisheries' conservation projects. However, the FLAG plans a project for a fisheries mentoring program to promote fisheries to young adults.

2.3.3 Evaluating policy structures and discourses

While Åland is an autonomous region with its own government and parliament, main policy lines are outlined in the Finnish operational programme of the EMFAF 2021-2027. All business related to internal affairs fall under the competence of the Åland parliament, and Åland has its own fishing legislation from 1956. Decision making regarding the quota fish species (Baltic herring, sprat, Baltic salmon, and cod) are made at the international level, but management of fishing regarding other fish species, such as pikeperch, pike and perch, is in the responsibility of provincial government, through legislation and its implementation, and the local water owners – either by their associations or individual water owners.

The EU common fisheries policy sets the framework for regulating and supporting commercial fishing. Fishing quotas are determined within the EU management system and in cooperation with the Finnish Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. Environmental agreements and EU directives also affect fisheries governance, especially in relation to opportunities for mitigating the severe effects of grey seals and cormorants on the fishing livelihood. Åland's policy in implementing EU Bird directive in granting derogation permits for protective hunting of the cormorants has been more liberal and less bureaucratic than in other parts of Finland.

When the right to hunt seals in a controlled manner as a protective measure was introduced at the turn of the millennium, it was only granted to fishermen to help them cope with the problems induced by seals, as an extra possible income. However, lack of time quickly emerged for hunting, hence fishermen asked for the hunt to be set free which happened in 2008. Today, the controlled hunting of seals and cormorants takes place on hunters' own initiative and no personal permits or applications are required. Policies that exist are the hunting permits for seals and cormorants taken annually on the grounds of protecting fish stocks and fisheries. Although controlled hunting permits are justified to protect other species and fishing, it is nevertheless enshrined in the permits as important that any catch from the hunt should be utilized as food or otherwise. This is challenging because of the EU trade ban on seals and writings in the bird directive that regulates cormorants. The controlled hunting system is judged to work quite well, even for species other than seal and cormorant and the controlled hunting contribute to the tolerance of seals and cormorants. There was a concern in the beginning that controlled hunting would compete with seal safaris for locations in the sea but there has never been a complaint which is a good mark to the hunters.

Generally, Åland and its fisheries office (Fiskeribrådan) aims at supporting fisheries livelihoods together with their competitiveness, profitability, ecological and social sustainability. Policy documents describe trends and conditions, but there are, however, no strategic plans that would concretize the society's targets, actions, and remedies, regarding the steep decline of professional fisheries. Fisheries issues are not mentioned in the TCL municipalities' strategic plans and documents. Moreover, few municipalities provide facilities that fishers can use for ice production, cooling or freezing and provided fishers access to wharfs and shores.

It seems that the support for fish farming has become shadowed by strengthened environmental ethos. In several rural places fish farming in open net cages is very important for the local community from a social and economic perspectives, providing jobs, infrastructure, and taxes. Environmental targets for nutrients in the sea are in direct conflict with aquaculture, which creates public debate. The target in the aquaculture strategy is to increase fish farming production until 2030, simultaneously environmental production targets are becoming stricter forcing increased production in practice towards closed circulation (RAS) to avoid nutrient leakages.

Regarding EU policy, the Åland government and the politicians have negotiated an exception of the Baltic cod fishing ban into a research quota for the Ålandic fishers. Interviews touched the drift net ban made in the Baltic Sea in 2008 which is considered unjust by fishers and wrecked the salmon fisheries. The intervention was not compensated, neither in money or nor salmon quotas. Alternative methods to drift nets (anchored nets, pontoon trap nets) are not nearly as functional in the Åland setting. The ban was justified by protection of porpoises, but this species has not often frequented the Åland archipelago. Bärkraft.ax, a sustainability network formed in 2016 keeps a public eye on the environment, waters and fish population and brings their concern to the government level.

Participation and 'voices'

It is considered 'farfetched' for the fisheries sector to participate in what is perceived as a bureaucratic administration and decision-making, yet there is a flexible and short space between the grass-root level and the governmental authorities and politicians. Representatives for fish farming and the Fisheries Agency, based on the Aquaculture Strategy, wish to increase the conditions of activity for fish farming, however, this is opposed by the Environment Agency and environmental NGOs. Large-scale trawling is supported by authorities and trawling operators and to some extent by fish farmers, yet opposed by the Environment Agency, environmental NGO, the anglers, and coastal occupational fisheries.

Mapping formal and informal structures in fisheries communities

The fisheries sector is a cornerstone of the Ålandic intangible heritage; hence the structures of influence and power are intertwined during centuries. Today formal structures exist, e.g., water owners' fisheries associations, Åland fishers' association, Åland fish farming association, an inter-municipality group for the interest to support wind power development on Northern Åland.

Informal structures both in private networks but also in official context within the municipalities, and social contexts e.g., village shops, cafés etc. The local media has a strong influencing power and societal control on decision making (overall) on Åland. The local press (2 major newspapers and public service radio) actively covers societal activities, including fisheries, nature, and environmental changes. The media follows the democratically elected politicians and parties (re-elected every fourth year) and displays obscurities when they occur.

Social media on the other hand is part of the new, both formal and informal, influencing and tools. Fisheries, environment, and nature challenges are still debated officially in traditional media, hence social media is more used for marketing fisheries activities and posting memories. Proposals from the government are sent on referral to official bodies for consideration including fisheries actors e.g. Ålandsfiskare, Ålands fiskodlarförening, ÅNM, Eckerökortet. Citizens can also comment on proposals through the official system.

2.3.4 Analysis

Problem statements for the fisheries communities within the TCL can be categorised as conflict situations between the fishers and other actors. Sixteen years ago (Neuman 2007) the conflicts were perceived by the people living outside the capital as conflicts of great importance between fishers and water owners (29%), fishers and nature conservation (26%), fishers and authorities (22%), between fishers (13%) and between fishers and non-fishers (11%). In our interviews we have reached all the above-mentioned groups and the perception is still that the 'conflicting' parties are the same with equal values. Fishing, hunting, boating, and general coastal living is part of an important intangible cultural heritage for Ålanders. There is, however, a growing concern that this knowledge is being lost with urbanization and lifestyle changes and fewer people than ever take their sustenance from the sea.

EU regulation (e.g., seal and cormorants), Finnish legislation (e.g., fishing quotas) and Ålandic legislation regulate the fisheries sectors on Åland. There are no self-determining rights for the fishers per se while major self-determining power lies with the organized water owner associations where decisions are taken commonly at yearly general assemblies; decisions made primarily by owners and not (only) by local fishers. However, often there are connecting denominators between fisheries' and water owners' interests.

Seals and cormorants play a major role and effect the fisheries sector but there are numerous other things that are also important. For example, eutrophication is problematic in the entire Baltic Sea and has visible effects on the Åland Islands. The spawning grounds for fish get overrun by filamentous algae that thrive in the nutrient rich waters and suffocates the seabed. This, in combination with predation, means that fish stocks and local populations of fish have a difficult time recovering even if fishing by humans is stopped altogether or become highly restricted. There are however areas where fish thrive and, in these areas, conflicts are likely to occur when the competition for the resource intensifies. This have in some cases resulted in people being restricted from fishing when private water owners become more protective about their resources.

A conflict is also visible regarding EU directives and Finnish state law and quotas. One major cause is in the way salmon fishing is regulated with the ban on driftnets and the size of the quota regarding rest of Finland. There is also concern about the large-scale fishing of Baltic herring which is raised as a threat by environmentalists, coastal fishers, anglers, and certain governmental officials alike.

2.4 TCL Report: Ireland

By Alex Miller

2.4.1 Introduction

The Irish Transition Coastal Lab (TCL) is focused on the coastal region of the Connemara Gaeltacht, a largely rural area west of Galway City. Coastal Connemara is a location of inter-sectoral competition and changing demographics due to economic and industrial shifts in the region. Home to the largest Gaeltacht (Irish language speaking community) on the island of Ireland, Connemara is a geographic region that has historically featured as a wild landscape with a distinctive history and culture and strong links to the Irish diaspora.

The coast of Connemara is experiencing increasing pressures from Blue Growth, such as proposed aquaculture and energy developments. Tourism intensification on the Wild Atlantic Way (WAW), Blue Growth developments, and a strong sense of local identity, has resulted in contestation over the future of coastal areas (Pafi, 2021).

Summary of research participants by sector:

Stakeholder sector	Number
Community	4
Voluntary sector – NGOs	0
Public	3
Private	2
Other	1

2.4.2 Understanding the community:

The Irish TCL is focused on the coastal areas of the Connemara Gaeltacht in County Galway. The Galway Gaeltacht covers extensive parts of County Galway, stretching from Baile Chláir east of Galway City to Cloch na Rón in West Connemara, a distance of approximately 100km (Galway County Council, 2022). The Gaeltacht stretches north to the border with County Mayo and includes the inhabited offshore islands, the Oileáin Árann (Aran Islands).

We have defined our Transition Coastal Lab as the coastal region stretching between Ros An Mhíl and Carna in the south Connemara region of County Galway. See figure below for a map of the case study area. Despite the relatively small area of the case study, the communities within our TCL are not homogenous, nor are they facing the same challenges in each area. Different villages and communities experience different levels of investment, infrastructure, tourism, and natural resources.

Figure 7 Map of the Galway Gaeltacht, the focus of the Irish TCL.

South Connemara is noted for its rich cultural, linguistic, and maritime heritage. The region is made up of poor agricultural land and has historically had few employment opportunities aside from small scale farming and fishing (Ó Sabhain and McGrath, 2020). The cutting and harvesting of turf (dried peat, extracted from peat bogs) and seaweed are traditional subsistence activities in Connemara which continue today (Pafi, 2021). The region has higher than average levels of unemployment, underemployment, poverty, and an ageing demographic structure, with many young people leaving to find work in other regions of Ireland or emigrating internationally (Ó Sabhain and McGrath, 2020). Our local partner, Údarás na Gaeltachta, is an Irish government agency which is responsible for the economic, social, and cultural development of the Gaeltacht regions of Ireland. Údarás na Gaeltachta has coordinated Language Planning Processes in Gaeltacht areas. Language Planning entails working with local community representatives to develop integrated language plans which aim to enhance the use of the Irish language in the home, the community, in education, social, business, and public structures

The Irish TCL includes 4 Language Planning Areas: Cois Fharráige, An Cheathrú Rua, Ceantar na nOileán, and Conamara Láir. While each of these areas are in the Gaeltacht, the level of Irish fluency and the use of Irish as the primary language varies between communities. Based on the figures taken from the 2016 census provided by Údarás Na Gaeltachta, there are 14,054 people living in the TCL area.

Gaeltacht regions differ from many population centres in Ireland as Gaeltacht villages are rarely built around a village centre, but rather tend to be dispersed over a larger area, with many single houses surrounded by small fields or bogland (Ó Sabhain and McGrath, 2020). The Gaeltacht region is home to an array of Irish summer colleges where students attend immersive Irish language classes and stay

with local Irish-speaking families. These summer colleges are an important source of income for host communities (Pafi, 2021).

Limited road access in some areas of coastal Connemara meant that the primary source of trade and travel was conducted by boat until the 1950s (Ó Sabhain and McGrath, 2020). Road infrastructure remains limited in the region, with the state of roads and bridges being identified by several participants as a limit on opportunities for investment and development in the area. Some of the TCL area is within commuting distance from Galway City, which brings its own unique challenges including increased demand for housing, heavy traffic, and demographic changes (Pafi, 2021).

2.4.3 Evaluating policy discourses

There are various issues facing the communities of the Connemara Gaeltacht. This section summarises some of the key areas which were raised by participants through the interviews and Q Sorts as well as those identified through the policy document review.

Unemployment and outmigration

A recurring discourse that was referenced during interviews and Q Sorts was the issue of employment opportunities, particularly for young people in the TCL. There is a pattern of young people leaving the area to work in other parts of Ireland or emigrating internationally. This is reflective of a larger trend of emigration in Ireland which is interlinked with housing affordability and other socioeconomic challenges. Outmigration from the Gaeltacht is considered a particular issue due to concerns over the viability of the Irish language as the primary community language in the area. The protection of the linguistic and cultural heritage of the Gaeltacht and the promotion of Irish as a community language is a policy objective for local and national government organisations (Galway County Council, 2022). With regards to the Ros an Mhíl area, Foley et al note: “According to the Pobal HP Deprivation Index the Ros an Mhíl harbour area is considerably more disadvantaged than the country as a whole. The unemployment rate in 2011 was almost 30% compared to a national annual average of 14.6%” (Foley et al., 2016).

Job creation and blue growth

Many of the proposed schemes to address unemployment in the TCL can be considered to be part of a larger blue growth discourse, as they centre around the use of marine and coastal resources for economic development. There are corrective policies especially in promoting cooperatives, social enterprises and community tourism. Several examples are listed below:

Páirc na Mara: Several initiatives have been instituted by organizations from across the TCL to enable job creation and address the persistent issue of unemployment and outmigration. One such initiative is Páirc na Mara, proposed as Ireland’s first dedicated Marine Innovation Park. Údarás na Gaeltachta is leading the Páirc na Mara as an effort to provide employment opportunities in the Kilkieran / Carna region. The Páirc na Mara development is presently stalled due to a planning refusal on environmental grounds from An Bord Pleanála, the state planning agency. Údarás na Gaeltachta plans to appeal the planning decision.

Tourism and the Wild Atlantic Way: Tourism is seen as a key source of rural economic development opportunities, particularly by Galway County Council, who cover the subject thoroughly in the Galway County Council Development Plan 2022-2028. “The tourism industry plays an extremely important role in Gaeltacht and Islands communities. The area has attracted a large number of visitors due to its unique landscape and facilities in relation to water-based activities, outdoor pursuits and cultural activities. The Wild Atlantic Way has developed over the years with increased signage and facilities along the route to attract and retain visitors to the area” (Galway County Council, 2022, p. 401).

Offshore wind development: In 2020, the Irish government set a target of delivering 5 GW of offshore wind energy by 2030, which will contribute to Ireland's target of generating 70% of its electricity from renewables by 2030 (Roux et al., 2022). The Sceirde Rocks Windfarm is a proposed offshore wind project, located off coast of Carna in the TCL area. The 450 MW wind farm would be one of the first offshore wind farms on Ireland's west coast. Galway County Council and other state agencies view offshore wind and marine energy as a significant source of potential economic growth: "It is expected that in the years ahead as offshore renewable energy development gains pace that the marine sector has the potential to make a very significant contribution to the climate change agenda on an international scale" (Galway County Council, 2022, p. 270).

Port expansion to support offshore industry: Údarás na Gaeltachta is supporting the expansion of Ros an Mhíl harbour, presently a fishing harbour with ferry service to the Aran Islands, as a key site of development for the expansion of Ireland's offshore wind sector. A report published by Údarás na Gaeltachta expects up to 900 jobs as a result of the development at Ros an Mhíl (Údarás Na Gaeltachta, 2023). Given the focus on the blue growth agenda, our TCL is a strong candidate to understand the opportunities for community-led development and how communities may benefit from blue growth in a sustainable and just way.

Social enterprises: However, the Údarás na Gaeltachta *Social Enterprise Development Strategy* aims to build awareness of the sector across the Gaeltacht; grow and strengthen social enterprises, especially by building their capacity; aligning spending programmes across agencies to support emergent and established social firms; and better evidencing their social value and impact. Údarás have a small grants programme and see the sector important in achieving balanced development, community legitimacy and a fairer and more inclusive economy.

2.4.4 Mapping structures:

The key institutions and structures in the case study area include local government, cooperative and community organisations, and the private sector.

Governance Level:	Name & example of key policy
National	<p>Government of the Republic of Ireland: Ireland is a constitutional republic with a parliamentary system of government. Key policies include marine planning, national spatial planning, transport and tourism.</p> <p>Key policy: Harnessing our Ocean Wealth - Integrated Marine Plan for Ireland</p> <p>Regional development including Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy 2020-2032 (RSES) which provides the roadmap for coordinated regional development.</p>
Regional	<p>Western Development Commission regional development authority for the west of Ireland</p> <p>Key policy: Coordinating marketing and promoting inward investment; in market intelligence; research on the performance and needs of the regional economy.</p> <p>Northern and Western Regional Assembly, representative regional authority responsible for regional planning policy and structural fund coordination.</p> <p>Key policy: Development of the BMW Regional Operational Programme; Mid-West Area Strategic Plan 2012-2030</p> <p>Údarás na Gaeltachta is the regional authority responsible for the economic, social and cultural development of the Gaeltacht.</p> <p>Key policy: Social Enterprise Development Strategy; Ros a Mhíl Strategic Enterprise Zone - Masterplan Executive Summary</p>
Local Government	<p>Galway County Council (Irish: Comhairle Chontae na Gaillimhe) is the authority responsible for local government in County Galway, Ireland. As a county council, it is governed by the Local Government Act 2001. The council is responsible for housing and community, roads and transportation, urban planning and development, amenity and culture, and environment.</p> <p>Key policy: Galway County Development Plan 2022-2028</p>
Cooperative	<p>Comharchumann Mhic Dara</p> <p>Key policy: Language Plan - An Cheathrú Rua</p>
Community	<p>Comhairle Ceantar na nOileán</p> <p>Key policy: Language Plan - Ceantar na nOileán</p>
Community	<p>Conamara Láir</p> <p>Key policy: Language Plan - Conamara Láir</p>
Community	<p>Fóram Chois Fharraige um Pleanáil Teanga CTR</p> <p>Key policy: Language Plan - Cois Fharraige</p>
Cooperative	<p>Comharchumann Shailearna Teoranta</p>
Cooperative	<p>Comhlacht Forbartha Inis Meáin Teo.</p>
Private Sector	<p>Arramara Teoranta – Seaweed Factory</p>
Private Sector	<p>Fuinneamh Sceirde Teoranta – Offshore Wind Developer</p>

2.4.5 Decision making structures and policy processes

From the review of policy documents and data collection through the interviews and Q Sorts, it is apparent that two of the dominant institutions in our TCL are the Galway County Council and Údarás na Gaeltachta. Both institutions have policy agendas which prioritise economic development in the region while recognising the significance of the Irish language to the social and historical fabric of the region. There appears to be a grassroots desire for employment opportunities, as evidenced by local social media campaigns and raised by several research participants.

In addition to these two government institutions, community groups and co-operatives play a key role in the local economies of the Gaeltacht region, acting as enabling bodies for many community activities and providing avenues for political representation within the broader governance network. Supporting capacity building in community and co-operative groups may be an opportunity for the EmpowerUs project to explore throughout the remainder of the project.

2.4.6 Crosscutting issues in the Lab

As noted, there are many policy priorities at play in the TCL. Local residents in the TCL have expressed concerns about unemployment and outmigration, which impacts on the viability of the Irish language in the Gaeltacht. Economic development is prioritised as a way to provide employment and therefore stop the decline of the Irish language, as envisioned in reports and policy documents by Údarás na Gaeltachta and Galway County Council. This economic development agenda is centred largely around the idea of blue growth and the blue economy. There is potential in the TCL for different conceptualisations of development and growth to come into conflict with each other (i.e., between fisheries and the development of offshore wind, or between aquaculture and tourism). These potential sources of conflict will need to be considered as the EmpowerUs project continues its work in the TCL if we are to develop a well-rounded understanding of the situation in the region and what needs to be done to enable sustainable and just community-led development.

2.5 TCL Report: Norway

By Vida Maria Daae Steiro and Christian Buschmann Ekeland

2.5.1 Introduction

The Træna TCL is a municipality in Nordland County, Norway. It is part of the Helgeland traditional district. The administrative centre of the municipality is the island/village of Husøya. There is also a population center on the island of Selvær, and two inhabitants living on Sanna island. The main industries in Træna are fishing and processing, tourism, and aquaculture. Træna is a dynamic community with a 9000-year history. Current demographic and industrial changes bring challenges and opportunities for the Træna community. The profile of respondents is shown below but in addition to these structured interviews informal meetings and interviews were also conducted with stakeholders including: Community = 2; Voluntary sector = 1; Public = 2; and Private = 1.

Summary of research participants by sector:

Stakeholder sector	Number
Community	4
Voluntary sector – NGOs	4
Public	11
Private	5
Other	0

2.5.2 Understanding the community

Træna is a municipality consisting of several islands, 33 nautical miles from the shoreline in Nordland County, northern Norway, with an area of 16 km². It is accessed by car ferry and speed ferry only. With its approximately 450 inhabitants, Træna is the 4th smallest municipality in Norway by population. The population is mainly living on the two islands Husøya (400 people) and Selvær (50 people). Electricity is transmitted from the Reppa power station on the mainland by a submarine power cable.

There is a kindergarten and a primary school, located on Husøya, and children from Selvær take the local boat. Beyond grade 10, students must move to the mainland for high school, although not to the same place. Many do not move back again, often due to a lack of job opportunities relevant to their education.

There is no hospital in the municipality, but the local general doctor resides on Husøya. Additionally, there is a municipal nursing home. There is a church on Husøya, and a small chapel on Selvær. However, the church does not play an exceptionally big role in the community. The local museum is a central institution that organizes a range of events for all, often in cooperation with the Træna festival. Husøya has a restaurant/pub, a café, one grocery store, a flower and laundry store, a gym, a pool, a youth club, a hotels/tourist cabins and a ceramics workshop. The cornerstone company is Pelagia, a fish processing plant.

Figure 8 Map of Træna municipality. The majority of the population lives on Husøya, approximately 50 people live on Selvær, and two people live on Sanna. (Source: Thorsnæs, G. & Engerengen, L., 2023. *Træna*. Store norske leksikon. Available at: <https://snl.no/Tr%C3%A6na>).

About half of the workforce is employed by the municipal government, the majority in human health and social work (18% of total workforce) (Statistics Norway, n.d.). Other municipal employment includes public administration, education, and construction. The remaining half works in the private sector, mainly in manufacturing (24% of total workforce). Fishing and agriculture (including aquaculture) represents 18% of the employment in Træna (Statistics Norway, n.d.). Between the 1980s and the 2010s, the number of registered main occupation fishers in Træna municipality decreased from around 90 to below 40 people (Directorate of Fisheries, n.d.). Today, one woman and 31 men are registered main occupation fishers in Træna. The agriculture and fishery, construction, transportation, and manufacture industries are male-dominated, while the education, retail, human health and social work and public administration/defence/social security are female-dominated occupations in Træna (Statistics Norway, n.d.).

Although the cultural sector is not the largest employer, it is important in ways that affect quality of life and what happens outside of work on Træna. The social element of the municipal master plan also highlights the vulnerability of relying on few companies, and that the cultural sector is an important part of diversifying the economy (Træna municipality, 2017). Many of the local businesses earn a large proportion of their sales during the yearly music festival “Trænafestivalen”. This is an internationally known festival, attracting 2000-5000 visitors for a week every summer (before covid-19) (Horjen, H.W., 2014). Trænafestivalen could be seen as an anchor institution. It is greatly involved in financially supporting other activities on the islands, including the youth club and collaborations with the museum. It also organizes the pride parade during the festival. Locals are greatly involved, both in volunteer work and as festival attendees. The rest of the year, the local volunteer spirit is great amongst generally a core group of involved people, who arrange a range of activities open to locals

and visitors alike. Many inhabitants are members of several of the more than 20 local community groups, which arrange activities and contribute to the social glue (Straube, 2019).

Economic diversification is central to the municipal masterplan of 2017 and recently, large investments have led to the current construction of the land based post-smolt facility “Gaia” and soon the Træna 365 hotel, aiming for year-round tourism. The main challenges for community development on Træna relate to its distance from the mainland. Its location creates additional costs for anything that needs to come from the outside. It also leads to challenges for the municipality in providing the services that they are legally required to, because of the additional cost caused by distance (Frisvoll et al., 2015). After the municipal reform of 2014-2017, Træna was categorized as an “involuntary small municipality”, due to its distance from other municipalities preventing its merging with others. Træna is now part of an island municipality project, which is a cooperative planning project between three island municipalities that seek to take advantage of their opportunities and competitive advantages while meeting challenges related to demography, recruitment and additional costs not compensated for in today’s system. They also sent their input to the advisory of today’s “generalist municipality system”.

Træna as ‘project-run’ municipality

Municipal employees themselves raise the issue of being a project-run municipality, and believe it has its pros and cons. Being dependent on project funding, much of the work they do is steered by what kinds of projects they are part of. This means that they are not necessarily free to govern the way they want to, or focus on the most pressing issues, because they need to fulfil the objectives of the projects they are part of. Sometimes, this leads to relevant and important outcomes for the community. The funding opportunities often come from the county level, and are informed by national strategies, but also issues related to conditions in rural areas of Norway in general. These often align with Træna issues. Being a “project-run” municipality also has some downsides in that people may become “tired” of projects. In addition, there is a high overturn of people, many of whom have initiated important development and community projects, that in some cases disappear when the initiator moves away from Træna. In other cases, someone else “takes over” the concept, with or without their own adaptations, or the project leads to synergy effects.

In 2015, the development project “Tenk Træna” was initiated because of the threat of a shutdown in one of the main fishery-related companies in the municipality in 2012. Due to the vulnerability of having little diversity in economic activity, the project aimed to develop activities that would create new jobs, as well as immigration to Træna. By the end of its first period, in 2017, Tenk Træna led to the establishment of several cultural projects that created “bolyst” and 7 people moving to the islands (Flatnes, 2017). Related to place attractiveness, “bolyst” may be defined as the desire to live/stay in a place or to move to a place. In addition, it supported the establishment of new businesses such as algae farming and a company that aims to recruit and support young fishers. The project was therefore extended by 3 years, with continued support from the county. The innovation work in Træna municipality led to it receiving the innovation prize from the Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development in 2018. However, data from *Statistics Norway* show that the population has continued decreasing from its most recent high of 506 in 2012 to 444 at the end of 2022.

2.5.3 Key issues and policy discourses

Træna is experiencing a housing shortage. According to the local politicians and administration, about 50 houses in Husøya and Selvær are empty most of the year, except a few weeks during the summer, when the owners are there for the holiday. This is a great issue because there is no available housing, neither for those who want to move to Træna, nor for those who rent and want to buy a house. It also creates challenges in employing people from outside Træna, as there is no available housing for newcomers. Due to distance from the mainland, building a house has high cost, while the value of

houses is low. This leads to difficulties in obtaining loans for building houses. The housing shortage is also a topic of tension between the municipality and private business. Housing availability is also a challenge in other Nordland County districts, and a priority topic at the county governance level (Nordland County council, 2013).

Transportation challenges were raised by all informants as a significant issue in Træna. Due to Træna's location, it is difficult to get to and from, and winter storms often lead to boat cancellations. People's main concerns are communications between Husøya and Selvær, and the lack of correspondence to other transportation alternatives once on the mainland. Ferry transportation is regulated by the county, which divides its budget between the many island communities along the Nordland County coast. Their priorities are often criticized and protested locally, while the Nordland County politicians' decisions are subject to a nationally distributed budget, with which they try to accommodate all. Inhabitants get frustrated that the ferry lines regularly change, and that the boat size was reduced, leading to less resilience to rough waters, and thus cancellations. This issue has also been subject to tensions between the two islands Husøya and Selvær. People from the less-inhabited island, Selvær, are frustrated by the experience that the municipality prioritizes Husøya in political argumentation with the county, and in their local decision-making.

A related concern raised by informants is the lack of integration of seasonal workers into the local society. Data from *Statistics Norway* shows that around 20% of the population is Polish, a majority of which are seasonal workers. In the social element of the municipal master plan (political plan), there is a focus on diversity and a goal of having a strategy for including new inhabitants, including refugees (Træna kommune, 2017). However, many don't think the integration is currently successful. Also, of the two large development projects that are being built here (Gaia and the Træna 365 hotel), some informants fear that future workers won't live on the islands, but commute. Although Gaia wishes to recruit local labour, there is mainly a need for engineers, which may be difficult to find locally. It is unknown who the new hotel will be employing (Forbord, 2022).

Climate change was mentioned by some informants as a potential challenge. More unstable weather conditions could be a threat to tourism development. Climatic changes could also threaten the population of Selvær (about 50 people), as the local commuting boat does not run in bad weather. Last year was a stormy one causing many cancellations – putting pressure on the local community of Selvær especially. The natural beauty of Træna is one of the factors providing opportunities for tourism development. The iconic mountains of the island Sanna are often subject of photos promoting Træna as an attractive place, especially in the marketing of Helgeland region as a tourist destination. The mountains, and the cave, are also heavily marketed in relation to the Træna festival, and arguably, contributes to “putting Træna on the map”. While production and manufacturing facilities are present and under construction, interviewees did not raise concerns with conflicts between these and tourism with regards to disruptions of scenic views. Some companies are more integrated into the community than others, and their marketing portrays them in “harmony” with their surroundings. Nova Sea, which has fish cages along the coast, has for example, been portrayed with a photo of lit-up fish cages at night, surrounded by northern lights and the Sanna mountains (<https://heilehelgeland.no/pa-jakt-etter-et-nytt-eventyr/>). With new development projects being established, new photos that present construction plans combine the landscape beauty with big factory buildings in a way that makes it look elegant.

Locally, economic development is framed as a necessity both for creating jobs and for maintaining a permanent society in the islands. Some informants see no other option than to say yes to new development projects, because nothing else will lead to new jobs and more opportunities. Even if it may lead to disruptions in the natural landscape, it seems that other issues are more pressing than

that of the natural ecosystem. This includes the perceived threat of the school shutting down due to a decrease in student numbers, with domino effects on the society.

By county politicians and regionally important business institutions, 'growth' is one of the recurring words of importance when speaking about the current and future (Nordland County council, 2013). So is 'sustainability', which is almost always included when talking about growth. There has to be growth, but it has to be sustainable – socially, environmentally, and economically. This is attributed to both regulations in the EU, the SDGs, consumer demands, and planetary limitations. The county plan for the period 2013-2025 puts "livskvalitet" (quality of life) as a first objective, viable communities and regions as the second, and value creation and competence as the third (Nordland County council, 2013). Strategies include developing resilient communities with well-functioning infrastructure, facilitating decentralized education opportunities, and stimulating new industries as well as restructuring and growth in already existing industries. Similarly, growth and job creation are important terms in national strategies as a means to sustain and develop rural Norwegian communities (Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development, 2021).

2.5.4 Mapping structures

On a national level, Norway has 15 ministries, all responsible for different sectors. Each ministry is responsible for policy making/ reforms within its domain. For the Træna municipality these ministries not only produce policies but also have supervision. The supervision is done at the regional level – the county. However, not all ministries have oversight duties versus the municipalities. The ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries is an example of such. The directorate of Fisheries has executive power as well as functioning as an advisory agent. The directorate monitors fishing activities, provides rules and regulations for fishing in Norway etc. The ministries also provide vital project funding. Applying for such funds often requires the municipality to implement reforms into their societal and area plans.

Within the domain of business development, the state also has an organization aimed to further entrepreneurship, called Innovation Norway. This organization is important because it provides fundings for start-ups and project development by local businesses. Træna municipality used to have a business developer in Moa Björnson. She is credited for a lot of the development successes like Gaia and Træna 365. The municipality can take a very active role in facilitating business development and Innovation Norway may provide funding as long as the projects are sustainable and aligned with state policy. As such, the ministries' policy making have huge impact on the municipal planning process and policy making.

The Træna TCL consists of three local clusters of stakeholders that play vital roles in place dynamics and development: the municipality, businesses, and community groups. First, is the municipality: It is governed by the municipal act and the main role is to provide services to its inhabitants. To provide education and health services are legally required activities of the municipality. Although not required by law, many small municipalities focus on projects that will strengthen local businesses and ensure an attractive living. The municipalities are obligated to co-create area plans and society plans (samfunnsplan) that outline the status of the municipalities and identify which areas of the society they want to develop by also listing measures to obtain these goals. Municipal planning follows the legally binding steps in the *Planning and Building Act*. In this act, there are certain requirements for participation that the municipality must follow. At specific points of the planning process timeline, citizens and stakeholders are invited to voice their opinion and participate. Each municipality has a political council that assesses the openness and quality of the work of the administration. There are also youth councils, and councils for elderly and people with disabilities. This is to ensure their impact on public projects and public plans. We were informed that the Træna municipality holds frequent public meetings about ongoing plans and happenings, both on Husøya and on Selvær. More people tend to show up on the Selvær meetings, than on Husøya.

Coastal zone planning has, since the growth in the aquaculture industry and related conflicts of area use in the 1980s, been an important governance tool along the Norwegian coast (Sandersen, 2018). Although municipalities are given the tools to lead an independent governance of their coastal areas, not all municipalities have sufficient planning resources and competency to independently develop holistic coastal zone plans. This is sometimes solved through intermunicipal planning. Between 2012 and 2019, Træna municipality was one of 13 municipalities in the Helgeland region that came together to cooperate on a holistic and knowledge-based coastal zone plan for an area of 10000 km², covering a length of coastline corresponding to about 5% of Norway's total coastline. This process led to updated coastal zone plans, although according to Sandersen, 2021, "genuine holistic intermunicipal planning was not actualized".

Municipal planning also adheres to the regional level. The process normally starts with a meeting with "planforum" organized by Nordland County. This is an assembly of the major stakeholder in any planning process from the Norwegian Public Roads Administration, the county governor, regional planning administration as well as representatives from the Sami Parliament, etc. The municipality has regulatory power but needs to adhere to these organisations. Normally the administration in a municipality is divided into sectors or departments like education, health, area and technical, culture and business development etc. However, in small municipalities there might not be enough funding for so some municipal leaders deliver a wide range of functions across their brief. In Norway the municipalities are mainly funded by the state through the General Purpose Grant Scheme (consisting of the general grant and income tax revenues) but this is per capita weighted, so the more people the more money each area receives. The highest political council is kommunestyret – the municipal council. Its composition is determined by elections every 4 years. This council also elects a mayor to lead them. One of the most important councils is formannskapet. It consists of the most prominent members of each political party. It can make some political decisions and they also manage and create the cases that come before the municipal council.

Secondly, the local businesses. There is no business association on Træna. However, there are several important businesses here that could have quite a lot of political influence. Pelagia is the cornerstone business of the municipality. However, two large companies are in the pipeline and will be finished during the EmpowerUs lifecycle. Local businesses cooperate with the municipalities - they may produce projects together. The municipality tries to the best of its ability to facilitate businesses in their development work in the hopes that this will generate jobs. Businesses are important actors in the municipal planning.

Thirdly, the community groups. These groups are important for the quality of life on Træna. These groups produce important cultural and social events through volunteer work. There is a Norwegian word for volunteer work called "dugnad". Without it, many events would not come to pass. The Træna festival is a community group (forening) and its importance for the Island group cannot be underestimated. Many of the more influential stakeholders that come to Træna would not be here if not for the festival - it plays an important role in recruitment. The festival has also donated 6 million NOK to development work over the years. Some of the community groups may not have much in terms of economic power but they are important in terms of cultural and social capital. Community groups are also pivotal in municipal planning.

A critical point here is that many of the stakeholders have several roles. They might be local politicians and hold leadership positions in important community groups or businesses. There are informal, dynamic networks that come into play - which may easily influence policy making.

2.5.5 Decision making structures and crosscutting issues in the Lab

There are different levels of stakeholders that either dictate or influence policy making. Based on the information above here is a short overview of these and their power positions:

- Ministries dictate policy, also provide funding, advice and supervision relating to municipalities.
- Træna municipality produce policy through their planning processes that are open and transparent. The influential stakeholder regarding policy: It should be mentioned that policies that trickle down from the ministries can relate to issues that arise in the bigger cities – the smaller municipalities can have a hard time relating to these and need to adapt alternative ways of dealing with the challenges. Hence there are possible conflicts here.
- Nordland county and their regional plans. For instance, they are responsible for the boat and ferry communications that are vital to Træna
- State directorates like Norwegian Public Roads Administration, the county governor, regional planning administration as well as representatives from the Sami Parliament, etc. When plans are either initiated or are sent out on public hearings these institutions can have objections or make suggestions.
- Regional political councils such as Indre Helgeland regionråd and the Island municipality project.
- All levels of governance are required by law to have an open hearing in planning processes.
- You also have stakeholders like regional DMOs (Visit Helgeland). As we do not have our own ministry of tourism in Norway these organisations can have quite the influence over policy making. In the Træna case, however, one rather complains about the lack of agency in this organization. It could be mentioned that development organizations like Kunnskapsparcken Helgeland and Rana Utvikling can influence policy making as they often can be facilitators of for instance the masterplan for tourism in the region.
- Local businesses like the cornerstone company Pelagia can assert influence in both single cases but also policy. In our Q sort survey several of the interviewees complained that the blue sector has too much power.
- NGOs also submit their ideas and criticisms within the public hearing rounds of planning processes.
- Community groups often provide services that enhance wellbeing in the municipality. They can have a lot of political capital even if they are run by volunteers. One informant said that the second most important person on the island group, apart from the municipal director, was the festival director.
- Then you have the un-affiliated individuals in Træna. To quote an informant: “they can have more impact on everything since we are so few people”.

Summing up, the municipality is the most important policy maker on the list as their policies directly concerns the sea people. But both the national and regional levels may dictate, hinder or change wanted policies. The local actors matter a lot in local policy making. Here, large companies seem to have the most influence. Also, community groups may have influence. Additionally, many individuals have many roles or have partaken in many important development projects. As one informant said: “The informal social networks can sometimes dissolve the democratic principles and lead to corruption”.

Due to the small number of inhabitants, the Træna community have a dynamic and strong way of influencing policy making. Policymakers are also community members, and informal dynamics influence formal governance. Thus, it is difficult to distinguish between “what the community wants” and discourses in local politics. Regarding policy, there are many conflicts on important policies in Træna: There is a growth policy, but currently there are no available houses in Træna.

There is a housing policy, but local companies (Except Træna 365) do not want to build houses and Træna is in the banks’ “red Zone” making it difficult for ordinary people to get loans. There is a communications policy- but here Træna is relying on the county and the latter loses money on the services they already have. There is an integration policy, but the foreign workers are there only seasonally and there is not enough work for them all year around.

2.6 TCL Report: Spain

By Silvia Gómez Mestres, Beatriz Patraca Dibildox, and Miroslav Pulgar Corrotea

2.6.1 Introduction

Cap de Creus is a peninsula on the Costa Brava in northeastern Catalonia, Spain, belonging to the province of Girona and the region of Alt Empordà. Its rugged coastline and rocky cliffs make it a popular attraction. In 1998, it became the Natural Park of Cap de Creus due to a social demand from the territory to preserve its exceptional natural and cultural heritage, including historical landmarks and archaeological sites.

Summary of research participants by sector:

Stakeholder sector	Number
Community	14
Voluntary sector – NGOs	7
Public	4
Private	15
Other	4

Cap de Creus is one of Catalonia's largest natural parks, encompassing the peninsula (11,000 ha) and its surrounding marine area (3,000 ha). The region's coastline is home to a diverse range of marine life, making environmental conservation a top priority for its inhabitants. As Spain's first marine-terrestrial natural park, the community faces challenges in balancing space use while defending social and ecological interests. At the maritime coastal forefront, The Park Natural of Cap de Creus comprises four villages, Roses, Cadaqués, El Port de la Selva, and Llançà, whose currently tourism-based economy replaced in the 2nd half of 20th century the traditional fishing and horticulture (Pi Sunyer, 1977), progressively displaced as subsidiary activities (Gómez and Lloret, 2017).

2.6.2 Understanding the community

Cap de Creus municipalities have diverse stakeholders, as their populations differ in number and composition. Roses is the largest community with a high population density, while Cadaqués is a popular tourist destination known for its cultural attractions and fishing heritage. Llançà has a low population density and is surrounded by two protected natural areas. Port de la Selva has the lowest population density and has undergone transformation due to tourism since the 1960s.

Figure 9 The Cap de Creus Natural Park and marine protected area

There are patterns of home and place-making among migrants from a middle to upper socioeconomic class, who are migrating from the Global North. These patterns are by what is understood to be a diaspora or a transnational community (Fàbrega, 2023). The figure shows a challenge to the traditional "economic immigrant" category. Retired European citizens are adopting coastal towns as their second residence, and in some cases, it becomes their main home. They tend to be an aging population that participate in social and environmental protection activities. Their main incentive for mobility is to enjoy the natural environment, and they often join entities that promote a healthy lifestyle in a healthy environment. Economic immigrants in Roses and Cap de Creus come from various countries, including Morocco, Algeria, and sub-Saharan African countries. They work in low-wage jobs like hospitality and construction and face social integration, language barriers, and exclusion challenges. Programs and initiatives are in place to promote social integration and inclusion, including language classes, job training, and cultural exchange programs. Non-profit organizations like "Creu Roja" and "Càritas" provide legal aid, counseling, and advocacy for Moroccan and other immigrants.

Cap de Creus has a strong tradition of associationism and volunteering in various activities, such as sports, arts, popular culture and environmental protection. Recently formed associations, such as "Plàstics 0" and "Platges Netes", focus on combating plastic pollution. The companies linked to recreational and sports activities in the sea also act as energizers and promoters of a healthy environment (Lloret *et al.*, 2021).

2.6.3 Stakeholder mapping

Cap de Creus TCL has a governance system based on co-management models and participatory processes for political decision-making. We are particularly interested in two governance models: the Cap de Creus National Park and the Cap de Creus Fisheries co-management committee. In the Natural Park of Cap de Creus, there are three governance corps with roles in the decision-making:

- The governing board: Town Councils, Catalan Government, Maritime Authority. Ensures well management of managers and approves the budget and activities' memory.
- The advisory board: Scientifics from the University, fishers, hunters, NGO can only decide if they give an opinion that managers will consider.
- The Managers: civil servants and techniques from the Catalan government, professionals, environmentalists and biologists and agronomists.

Small-scale fishing in Cap de Creus is regulated through a co-management committee, which includes small-scale fishers, scientists, NGOs, managers, and public administration. Their primary goal is to write a sustainable management plan for small-scale fishing in the area. To understand decision-making capacity, the governance structure of the Park will be considered, including actors from the private sector and community. The private sector is active beyond economic issues, and their involvement in social, cultural, and environmental projects is noteworthy.

2.6.4 Evaluating policy discourses

We evaluate three guiding documents concerning the Natural Park of Cap de Creus marine area. The first document is the Uses and Management Regulation Plan proposal of the marine area of the Natural Park of Cap de Creus (Gencat, 2023). The proposal, known as PRUG, is currently in an unfinished state as it is undergoing a collective participatory process. Its objectives include restoring and conserving natural processes and associated biodiversity, the preservation of habitats and species of particular interest, and conserving the landscape and environmental quality. The plan also aims to encourage economic and social activities that align with the restoration and conservation of the natural and cultural values of the space. Furthermore, it seeks to contribute to environmental awareness, education, and ecological and geological knowledge. While the participatory process has some stakeholders expressing disagreement due to economic or customary reasons, other active participants are concerned about state projects conflicting with the plan's environmental goals and EU environmental measures affecting fisheries.

The second document is DECREE 118/2018, of June 19, on the governance model of professional fishing in Catalonia (Generalitat de Catalunya; 2018). The governance model emphasizes co-management, ecosystemic, and adaptive management approaches to achieve Maximum Sustainable Yield (MSY) while preserving ecosystem services. The decree establishes co-management committees that rely on management plans and a participatory decision-making model. These committees foster collaboration among stakeholders, including fishers, to achieve consensus in decision-making processes.

The third document is ORDER ACC/46/2023, of March 13, approving the Fisheries Management Plan in Cap de Creus (Gobierno de España, 2023). This recently approved plan aims to manage marine resources and ecosystems in the Cap de Creus area through environmental regulations, coordination with relevant bodies and administrations, and establishing protection zones for fisheries management and the recovery of degraded ecosystems. The plan explicitly acknowledges the objectives outlined in the PRUG and aligns with its environmental policies. Notably, the plan addresses the concerns of artisanal fishers by including regulations and inspection measures to combat illegal fishing activities.

2.6.5 Mapping structures

Governance processes are inherently participatory, involving various actors in decision-making. These actors may belong to different organizational systems, such as park governance, co-management committees, or local citizen initiatives. These systems may operate within individual municipalities or form networks spanning the TCL region.

The Catalan Government created the Co-management committees in 2018 to establish comprehensive management plans for fishing and devolve management power to stakeholders. The co-management committees are involved in the governance of the sea and coast and include various actors in a participatory plan. The Committee for Co-management of Fishing at Cap de Creus (CPC) was created on January 14, 2021. The co-management committee meets monthly, but aside from these formal meetings, they have established informal permanent communication mechanisms such as Whatsapp, which allows for a direct and immediate line between the fishers and government representatives. Apart from an "agenda," the questions and comments spontaneously enable us to take the pulse of everyday concerns.

We detected informal structures of community networks linked to each other at the municipal level and the territory of Cap de Creus. They organize campaigns together in favour of some social or environmental cause. We also detected local leaders outside the institutional systems of governance who move between local and regional structures and have significant influence in the area. These stakeholders belong, in many cases, to sports associations or local businesses that are also involved in the care of the environment and other social aspects and generate cohesion in the network of actors in their respective municipalities.

2.6.6 Understanding policy processes

As previously mentioned, the link between public policies and society is, at least on paper, focused on stakeholders' participation in coastal regions and is open and accessible to the community. Recognizing the political will in the TCL of Cap de Creus case is essential, but the processes are still incipient. In the case of co-management committees of fisheries, direct dialogue speaks of a vertical model articulated through scheduled meetings and informal channels. Its main mechanism is consensus, an institutional success in this way is the approval of the fisheries management plan in the plenary session and its recent legal approval in March of this year. The Autonomous Government of Catalonia website mentions that *participatory processes are structured debates around public policies to incorporate citizens' voices in government decisions. The Government acquires the commitment to listen to them, incorporate them when appropriate and explain to the citizens the decisions made, enriched with this participation* (Gencat, n.d.). Contributions can be online, by attending face-to-face sessions, or by consulting other participants' contributions. Nevertheless, the Park's regulations, creates some tensions that, although they cannot always be classified as conflicts, generate a state of alert to comply with the provisions (Gómez, Carreño and Lloret, 2021). On the one hand, some socially and politically active stakeholders do not feel represented in the processes and express their disapproval through other informal channels, such as reporting on social networks under the hashtag #noalprug or information tents in the streets. On the other, and as occurs with all political processes, some inhabitants are part of the community but do not join these calls because they are unaware of them or due to a lack of interest.

Values are an essential force and legal tool in environmental governance. Economic activities should be considered part of the ecosystem and balanced with ecological, socio-cultural, and economic values. Conflicts between these values can arise, but it is essential to maintain a fair and sustainable balance. Integrating marine socio-ecological systems into policies is the solution to reconciling competing uses of marine resources (Gomez, 2022). Although we have no evidence of an administrative exclusion regarding ethnic origin, we note low participation of sectors from countries that do not belong to the European Union. Empowering and involving these sectors in the coastal community is important for our laboratory, since many participate in economic activities linked to the sea, especially during the tourist season.

3. Stakeholder perspectives: crosscutting themes

This section reviews the key cross-cutting challenges to community development, empowerment and capacities within the six TCLs. The purpose of the interviews and the policy analysis is to understand the barriers to local development; key assets and resources on which to build, how change impacts the capacity or power of local people to act and how common challenges affect a range of maritime communities across the EU.

3.1 Dis-embedding the coast

Each area has its distinct challenges, resources, political conditions and assets but, the analysis reveals a number of cross-cutting themes that relate to wider economic processes, ideas about blue growth and the effects that each has on the power of local people to act. The impact of blue growth is in part, a rationale for the wider EmpowerUs project and there are different, but related effects, that impact on the six case areas. The list is not complete but serves to frame the challenges for the Lab pilot, the implications for Nature Based Solutions and the efficacy of area-based (environmental, economic, social) development policies.

- **Demographic structure and sustainability:** A common strand across the Labs is the way in which complex demographic restructuring brought assets in terms of skilled workers and addressing gaps in the supply side of the labour market. However, it also created tensions with migrant workers from different cultural, linguistic, religious and ethnic backgrounds; pressures in the housing market; outmigration of young and better-educated people; and ageing, accelerated by retirement migration. The idea of community empowerment is clearly impacted by rapid and contradictory changes with the out-migration of young indigenous people and in-migration of older retirement and second homeowners in Connemara; and migrant workers in Træna and Cap de Creus for example.
- **Housing access and affordability:** The most significant effects are in the labour and housing markets and especially the lack of social and affordable housing within the indigenous community. The inability to stay and progress through the local housing market (as family circumstances change) is a challenge to the structure of the demographic base as well as the sense that coastal communities have a sustainable future.
- **Labour market restructuring:** The housing market is also linked to changes in the labour market. We have witnessed a significant shift in the economy of island and coastal communities from traditional primary industries in fishing and farming to more advanced circuits of (increasingly global) production in services, tourism and food processing. As noted below, it is not just about economic change, but about the loss of local identity associated with such traditions including salt extraction (Burgas); traditional forms of fishing (Åland); and seaweed cultivation (Connemara). The progress of these 'industrial waves' (Harvey, 2006) is not new and impacts on all communities, but are intensely experienced where traditions of work, heritage and identity shape the very idea of community solidarity.
- **Structural vulnerability:** Many peripheral coastal communities and islands are still reliant on a single economic sector or even a single employer. Diversifying the industrial base is critical but this is often presented to many coastal communities as a rationale for intensive and damaging forms of growth. How NBS can enable a sustainable economic transition of such weak economies clearly creates its own tensions and raises issues about what *type* of development is needed, how do local people benefit and how can it be sustainably managed in such sensitive ecosystems.
- **Connectivity and peripherality:** Many of the Labs are characterised by remoteness, even isolation, which is part of their attraction, but as we have seen services centralise (in both the private and the public sector), *connectivity* has become a more significant barrier to local development. Ferry connections, port/harbour capacity, reliable air links, IT quality, poor public transport and road infrastructure affect schooling, access to health facilities as well as the cost of doing business.

Clearly, there are tensions as infrastructure investment is a critical element in the physical, social and economic life of the area but at the same time opens development opportunities, second homeowners and tourists. Balancing development, especially in the context of NBS, will be important in each Lab pilot.

- **Environmental shocks:** Climate change is clearly understood across Lab areas including the effects of heat island effects (in Bulgaria), pollution discharge, level rises, eutrophication and algae cover, warmer waters and shorter ice cover periods. Storm surges and damage have increased in frequency and severity and as the analysis shows, protective measures are not implemented rigorously and are often bypassed by development, infrastructure and rezoning that leaves many ecosystems increasingly vulnerable.
- **Asset based development:** Each Lab community identified a series of structural development challenges, but also significant assets, especially *nature*, on which inclusive and balanced forms of development can be based. This included traditional industries in salt, seaweed and fishing; scenery and natural beauty; a rich cultural heritage; as well as a capacity to connect with the growth economy and innovation, using technology, to reduce the frictional effects of distance.

The concern for communities is that blue growth has been extractive and damaging but that economic transition is important across most of the Labs. Harvey (2010) uses the idea of *accumulation by dispossession* to characterise these processes, in which capital interests (indigenous as well as external) convert taken-for-granted natural resources (fish, salt, scenery, the sea and so on) into opportunities for commodification and profit. We see this with tourism, enabled by the redesignation of land uses and the provision of infrastructure (hotels, highways and development zones). But it has particularly intense effects on the coast by *disembedding* nature (land, lakes and the sea itself), work (especially in traditional industries) and finance (with external investors active across coastal ‘asset classes’) dominating the development agenda (Polanyi, 2001 [1944]). Polanyi sees this process of disembedding especially important in removing from local people, the levers of control over place. How the Labs respond, via the pilot, in re-embedding control over local development and nature within communities, is not the only question for the pilots, but emphasises the need to understand how policy can both transmit and resist such processes. This is considered next.

3.2 Forms of power in policymaking

EmpowerUs is fundamentally concerned with how *power* is enacted in coastal environments and how such communities can influence, resist and transform the processes that create uneven and exclusive forms of development. We noted that economic power, blue growth and global capital all impact on such development and narrow the agency that communities can exercise in such circumstances. However, we are also concerned with the different forms of power transmitted through complex policy processes impacting on coastal development.

Here, we draw on Healey’s (1990; 2010) work on land use planning and environmental management to identify ten distinct but overlapping policy processes at work across the TCLs. Again, the value of such analysis is that it aims to locate how and where power is enacted, the technologies that policymakers use to determine preferred spatial outcomes and where (and where not) it is more productive for communities to engage. Here, knowledge is explicitly political by arming the TCLs with an understanding of the different policy processes at work and how to engage in specific circumstances. The diagram below shows the complexity of decision-making processes, arenas and actors across the TCLs and it is useful to draw out the key issues for empowerment responses, especially in the design of the pilot interventions:

- It should be emphasised that each Lab is located within a liberal democratic structure in that politicians stand for election and are voted in or out depending on public preferences. If local

people do not like the way the coast is being managed, they can replace those in political charge. This might seem self-evident but the formal arena of representative politics remains a foundation of community mobilisation and influence.

- The discourse analysis below emphasises the importance of a technical basis for policy, especially at the local level. Statutory development plans, environmental designation and protective zonings are prepared in rational ways but offer significant and statutorily guaranteed opportunities for consultation and influence. Knowing how and when to participate in such regulated systems is clearly an important aspect of ‘technical’ empowerment.
- Blue growth regimes are detected across the policy hierarchy but especially in national and regional policies as well as in financial and fiscal instruments to incentivise private investment. Procurement, licensing and outsourcing systems have privileged private interests in the development of the coast and its resources. The rezoning of Urban Planning Zones in southern Cyprus to enable housing developments aimed to modernise the planning system in response to changing rural needs. However, it is also clear in the context of NBS that resource competition *within* the community (different forms of fishing, ownership, damage to habitats by different species and environment versus domestic fishing rights shows that the coast is not simply about exploitative blue growth regimes.
- The top-down management style noted across areas, but exemplified by Burgas, is practiced through bureaucratic and policy processes that are also political in their nature. This might be a form of *public entrepreneurialism* combined with a *market rational* approach but is achievable, in part, because local government is weak. Public entrepreneurialism is different and involves state capture of local initiatives, (nature-based) assets and commercial opportunities. Here, the local can be incorporated, bypassed or ignored, accentuating a sense of abandonment and powerlessness by communities who do not benefit from such forms of development.
- But bureaucratic systems also underpin significant protective rights, as noted below, emanating from a European level, beyond which the local authorities cannot act (at least in practice). These hierarchical tensions and how they are reconciled at the *local* (between economic development and environmental protection) are considered later and highlight the need to see policy processes, discourse and organisational structures as part of a coastal governance assemblage. But in Cyprus, proposals for an aquaculture zone and related land-based infrastructure highlighted the contest with environmental interests and the importance of land use designations in protecting coastal landscapes. The extension of the Vasilikos Energy Centre based on hydrocarbon reserves can be seen in the context of the designation of the Marine Protected Area as well as two separated protected forests. Statutory instruments offer leverage in NBS and give communities and environmental interests access to regulatory *power* at the coast. Interestingly, as the Cyprus case noted, licensing is used as a way of bypassing such restrictions, especially where decisions are removed organisationally from the local level and the people most affected by them.
- Semi-judicial power is also significant. Údarás na Gaeltachta proposed to develop Páirc na Mara as an innovative centre to use advanced aquaculture, with the community, to reposition Connemara around the growth economy. This had strong political, community and private sector support, but was refused planning permission by the central regulatory authority, An Bord Pleanála, primarily on environmental grounds. Counter appeals and a potential Judicial Review via the courts are being considered but here, decision making will be rules-bound, regulated and legally defined with specific actors with a *material* stake involved whilst the wider public, politicians and NGOs will not.

Processes	Decision making	Transition Coastal Lab	Structure
Pluralist politics	Competitive decision making within and between competing formal groups. Electoral weight, political ideology and resolution by vote.	Self governing island territories (Åland, Traena), regional assemblies (Ireland, Catalonia) municipal decision making (all).	Formal political structures shaped by representative democracy and electoral party-political power.
Clientist	Individuals with specific demands & a patron-client dependence, often framed by populist politics.	Rezoning and resource allocation to support property development in Black Sea ecosystems.	Informal and hidden political relations often characterised by corruption and lack of transparency.
Market-rational	Efficiency of the state, return on investment and minimising state costs.	Privatisation including salt production Burgas; off-shore energy Ireland; port infrastructure Traena.	Implementation via regularity instruments such as contracting-out, licensing, and policy directives.
Techno-rational	Technical experts define issues & priorities using expert knowledge & values.	Local development plan, zoning, ordinances & planning conditions, national park (S).	Nested in formal democratic structures such as municipalities, regional assemblies and national governments.
Bureaucratic-Legal	Legally-administratively defined interests, processes and decision making rules.	EU Nature 2000, LIFE, national designations and marine protected areas, fishing permits & licenses in all the TCLs.	Governance complexity, intersecting levels of rule-making creating tension with local, mainly <i>economic</i> , interests.
Judicial Semi-judicial	Legally defined actors, in administrative and adversarial forms of decision taking.	Planning appeals, public inquiries & judicial reviews. Parc Na Mara planning tribunal in Ireland.	Formal court & tribunals driven by legal rules & systems. Planning public inquires and oral hearings.
Bargaining	Individuals with specific demands with a patron-client dependence often framed by populist politics.	Rezoning and resource allocation to support property development in Black Sea ecosystems & coastal/rural Cyprus.	Participatory democracy, advocacy networks, civic society and environmental NGOs.
Corporatist	Mutual dependent parties in continued relation in order to maintain a dominant position.	Foreign direct investment in Ireland; property investors in Cyprus and Bulgaria; tourism in Traena.	Hidden routines between resource critical private actors not open to public scrutiny.
Open democratic	Expert, sectoral, area based interests in open discursive arena with expert opinion.	Community development, placed based and sectoral; parents associations; online network campaigns; sporting capital such as GAA in Ireland.	Loose networks in formal structural arrangements with varying degrees of legal certainty.
Special committee	Experts selected politically and administratively with a limited task based agenda.	Fisher associations, cooperative organisational forms, business associations, volunteering, co-management governance in Cap de Crues.	Specifically organised structures to deal with particular tasks/problems and selective actor involvement.

Figure 10 Policy processes and forms of power (Based on Healey, 1990, 2010).

- It should also be important to emphasise that many decision-making processes are simply not open to public scrutiny or happen well away from the coastal locations affected by the outworking of more corporatist modes of interest mediation. Global investor decisions and how they are mediated at the national and regional level, corruption and hidden alliances are difficult to ‘see’ but need to be acknowledged across the case sites. There are power processes that local people cannot observe, let alone influence.
- We also see bespoke governance arrangements in the form of special committees such as Fishers Associations, water owners’ associations, business associations and community networks that have a significant say in how policy is formed or resources allocated. Such processes, their attendant structures and the resources and legitimacy (representation) they hold also make them important sites of counter-power, resistance, and mobilising those negatively affected by ‘development’. As noted on Åland, small businesses attempting to diversify tourism into sports fishing have difficulty accessing such structures and the way in which vested interests regulate the licensing system. In other contexts, co-management committees have strengthened public participation in coastal management and fisheries in Cap de Creus.
- Linked to this is the everyday organisation of community groups, women’s networks, formal NGOs and alliances that have resisted development, held politicians and public officials to account, pushed back on area plans and developed independent economic, social and environmental projects that respond to local needs. This sector is also using social media to bring their networks together, organise rapidly and build a collective of interests on environmental risks (Catalonia), population loss of young people (Ireland) and recording local histories (Åland). Clearly, how such infrastructure can be strengthened and scaled – to be made more politically powerful – is a central task in the work of the pilots.

3.3 Understanding the structure of policy documents

The methodology section noted the importance of the policy evaluation to identify these strands but also their connection with the dominant narratives, linked to the discourses and rhetoric used to construct the respective coastal and maritime communities. To identify what the documents actually say and avoid selectively quoting particular narratives, key policies operating at the national, regional and local levels were subjected to a systemic discourse analysis using Leximancer software. The

documents subject to the analysis are set out in Annex II and contain (with expectations noted in the tables) comparative policies and programmes across each of the six TCLs.

Leximancer is a text mining tool to calculate and visualise themes emerging from interviews, policy documents and transcripts (Cretchely et al., 2010). Angus et al. (2013) show that it uses word frequency statistics (from all the words in a document) to generate their respective visualisations, as well as how topics relate to each other; and indicating which source files (the range of policy documents from each TCL) contain particular terms and concepts. Smith and Humphreys (2006, p.262) explain that it is a ‘method for transforming lexical co-occurrence information from natural language into semantic patterns in an unsupervised manner. It employs two stages of co-occurrence information extraction—*semantic* and *relational*—using a different algorithm for each stage. Hansson et al. (2010) point out that a particular strength of Leximancer is that it is intuitive in that it requires no *a priori* manipulation in terms of thematic coding so that categories emerge in response to the content of the text as data. It is appropriate here primarily because it can reveal the value base of the text and draws attention to the narrative – collections of words and related terms in the context of governance, values and how a range of stakeholders might express a particular ideological trope (Lin et al, 2020).

The diagram below shows the main concepts in national policy documents that show the dominant concept is about *development*: the *marine* as a zone primarily for economic and capital investments. This accounts for 22% of the content analysed and is closely related to *implementation* at 17%. We note below, the way in which policy discourses are often couched in terms of urgency; the economy is in crises and action is needed to make the transition to a different economic space. The Bulgaria *National Recovery and Resilience Plan* makes the connection between economic transformation, pro-growth logics and implementation:

Apart from being a tool for promoting economic transformation, the timely implementation of the program will also be a catalyst for the economic recovery of Bulgarian enterprises from the negative consequences of the economic crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

It is wrong to read ‘development’ as ‘blue growth’ but the content of the strategies also focuses on key economic sectors including energy (17% and the digital economy (11%). The Annex develops this analysis by populating the concepts with seeds so that the content of each one is clearer and also compares each level. A number of points emerge:

- Regional development policies (Annex III.I) also prioritise development but clearly connect with resource management priorities including, *fishing, water* and the *sea* as an asset. When the key concepts are looked at within *development*, familiar tropes emerge including *infrastructure* and the *economy*. But so too is the *environment, cultural heritage, social services* and as we move down the policy hierarchy, an evident concern for *people, the population* and *public services*.
- It is also useful to see connections between the concept of the *sea* as place, which as Annex III.II shows are concerned with fishing and development with little concern for gender, community or the precariat lives of many small-scale indigenous fishers.
- When we look at the concepts that *development* is related to, the correlation is strong with *infrastructure; municipal lead* (as the driver of development) and *fish, fishing* and the *sea* (as a resource asset).
- At the local level (Annex III.III), *development* again dominates but so too does *support*, a concern for the *area* and local *design*. *Support* is interesting as the concept is related to *rural, local, villages* and a concern for *heritage, communities* and the *natural* landscape (see the words identified in the table).

- Given the focus on blue growth and development in policy documents, Annex III.IV sets out the connection with identified concepts in a *Pareto* diagram that shows the order of importance attached to each one. It shows the connection with *planning*, the *marine* as a growth opportunity and infrastructure. However, as we go down the policy hierarchy, development and sustainability, villages, local and the public emerge more clearly. Environmental sustainability and the importance of local communities are not prominent at the national or regional level, which is where fundamental policy decisions, resources and laws tend to be exercised. If such concerns are not manifest as significant policy commitments nationally, their impact at a local level is, in crude terms, likely to be limited.

Concept	Hits	Percentage (%)
Development	2,450	21%
Marine	2,117	18%
Implementation	2,057	17%
Energy	2,008	17%
Digital	1,340	11%
Bulgaria	513	4%
Water	480	4%
Government	258	2%
Control	240	2%
Education	224	2%
Accordance	142	1%
Waters	119	1%
Total	11,948	100%

Figure 11 Thematic analysis of the selected national level policy documents across TCLs

3.4 Discourse analysis

Rydin (2003; 2007) emphasised the centrality of discourse in shaping planning policy, decision making and priorities for investment and more recently, Leipold et al. (2019) have warned about its use in comparative cases, where language, concepts and policy contexts will be different. For this reason and as noted earlier, emphasis was placed on standardising the methodology; discussing, understanding and calibrating the instruments (such as stakeholder mapping); and working through and testing the questionnaire (Annex I). Here, we use Rydin to understand the nature of the policy discourse and how it is rhetorically represented. This includes the use of *logos*, in that it is logical and rational to follow a particular policy line; *pathos* such as catastrophising the challenges of the Lab community and how it needs to change; and *ethos*, which asks more fundamental questions about who the coast is for and how do we get a more embedded and inclusive form of local growth.

The logic of blue growth

The diagram below shows a cluster of integrated discourses around blue growth, and how it is inevitable, even desirable, for coastal development. Here, the coast is an asset class, ripe for exploitation and accumulation. Energy, fish processing and tourism have been undercapitalised and if coastal communities are to survive, then rapid development of such resources is central to wealth creation. In Ireland, the marine plan is clear that this is about *Our Ocean Wealth* and how it is concerned with specifically economic value. For whom and at what cost is not fully explained. What is clear is that investment, infrastructure and innovation are critical to economic restructuring and it is logical, rationale and axiomatic that these technologies of growth are needed across decaying communities. In Ireland, Træna and Burgas, infrastructure (and state spending) on highways, bridges ports, industrial parks and innovation hubs are about de-risking sites and modernising the area for long-term investment. The gTECH labs in the Irish Gaeltacht and the Biological research centre in Åland reflect the need to connect backward and peripheral regions to the more advanced economy, not just the current wave of blue growth industries. Again, this in itself is not necessarily a problem but as noted below, how value is created and what impact it has on the local community is the challenge for effective forms of power and empowerment.

Crises and the need for intervention

Narratives of decay, decline and the need for urgent intervention are intimately connected with the growth discourse. As noted, the Burgas local development plan signals the transformation ‘from a post-socialist and depressive to an innovative and modern model of urban development.’ The pathos underpinning policy interventions and foreclosing other models of inclusive, slow or locally owned development shapes the scope and content of planning options and priorities for funding. Here, there is a disconnect between policy analysis and prescription so that out-migration is conceived of primarily as an economic issue (which is of course, significant) rather for the need to intervene in the housing market enabling more affordable, social, and locally owned tenures to compete with second homeowners, Airbnb’s and commuters. Competition between such sectors as well as between migrant workers and low-income indigenous communities is left largely to the market and in conditions those with the least resources lose out. Hardly surprising then that a related discourse is a loss of visibility in policy and politics among those who seem to be persistently losing out in such labour and housing markets. The loss of identity, traditions of work, language and cultures adds to the sense that local communities and all their complexity have been marginalised, even silenced in readiness for blue growth strategies. If they are useful to that growth in terms of work, sellable heritage or for consumption, then it is not a problem, but it is about how empowerment better positions them to resist and transform such conditions in more practicable ways.

RHETORIC	DISCOURSE	DISCURSIVE STRATEGY	REFLECTION
LOGOS An appeal to reason, logic and a rational, even self-evident justification for intervention.	Blue Growth	▪ A traditional growth-first logic in which maritime assets are collateral for development, exploitation and value extraction. These assets are under-capitalised and fail to meet their <i>economic</i> potential.	Sunny Beach Highway (B)
	Restructuring	▪ Traditional sectors, labour markets and ways of (artisanal) working need to be displaced in a processes of 'creative destruction' to enable the growth economy.	New port infrastructure (I, N)
	Modernisation	▪ Supporting infrastructure and connectivity necessary to make the adjustment from the old to the new economy and ready the coast for growth and exploitation.	City Within A City (C)
	Innovation	▪ Such modernisation needs to be future proofed by connecting the coastal political economy to new waves of production based on technology, service sectors and blue assets (fish, energy, aquaculture) & R&D.	University Biological Station Finstrom (F)
	Competitiveness	▪ The coastal economy needs to become more competitive to rival urban sites of production, anchored by a trope of outmoded processes and weak productivity.	Burgas PIRO local plan (B)
PATHOS A rhetoric of drama, crises and special circumstances in policy intervention.	Decay	▪ Some places are in terminal decline and without radical actions demographic, economic (especially labour market) while environmental decay will render communities unsustainable.	Nordland County Social Plan (N)
	Crises	▪ There is also an immediacy to the decay, especially in the form of environmental shocks, rapid depopulation, loss of assets (schools) and a need for policy (and political) urgency.	Endangered species (C)
	Recognition	▪ Places and people are rendered silent, insignificant, inarticulate or unimportant, ultimately delegitimising some communities, their cultures, ways of living and labour traditions.	Spatial language protection (I)
	Competition	▪ Intra-resource competition (between fishers, environmentalists; tourists, second home owners, migrant workers) undermine a collective sense of Lab community solidarity.	Users, environmentalists, tourism (S)
ETHOS Stresses ethics, morality and collective responsibilities in policy justification.	Value	▪ Uneven development and a concern for what is valued (see tradition and identity) how value is created, by whom, at what cost/effect and how is it captured within the Lab community.	Housing for local people (S, I, N)
	Ownership	▪ Linked to this, although not a strong trope, is ownership of the water, shoreline, economic entities, land, seaweed, wind, views and how it is secured for local people.	Water ownership rights (F)
	Identity	▪ Coastal life, traditional methods of work (fishing, salt, seaweed, language, culture in music, dance and literature, dress and a sense of place) are bound up in a distinct coastal imaginary.	Nature based identities (N,I, F, B, S)
	Protection	▪ The need to protect the environment from over-development, exploitation, climate effects and political indifference.	National Park (S)
	Curative	▪ The 'value' of the coast (water, air, sensory, views) need to be understood beyond monetized exchange.	'Curative' pools in Natura designation (B)

Figure 122 Discourses on coastal development and community empowerment

Resistance and alterity

It is certainly not the case that these processes are universally harmful or irresistible. In Bulgaria, NGOs have led an active campaign on environmental protection. Certainly, the pressures from over-development and industry are always present but Atanasovsko Lake represents an important site of political struggle about who and what the ecosystem is for and raising the problems, challenging developments and helping enforce directives also demonstrate the agency that communities have in such circumstances. The lake, views, salt and blue health are correctives to the commodification of nature value that disconnect local people from their experience of their home and the identity it engenders. These possibilities are shaped by three related discourses on community assets including value, ownership and identity. There is a consciousness about how we *value* the coast beyond opportunities for surplus, but as places with identities, histories and memories that are intrinsic to the people who live there. Profit is being made but is taken out of the coast, minimising its potential to create local multiplier effects and keep money recirculating within the *community* economy. Ownership makes the difference. In Åland, water rights are 'owned' only by local people; in Connemara, cooperatives and social enterprises have been supported by Údarás na Gaeltachta; and in Træna, community heritage including a local museum, are networked into similar projects across the Norwegian coast and islands.

3.5 Multilevel governance and coastal development

The stakeholder analysis, supported by the policy evaluation, emphasises the increasingly globalised nature of the development challenge, in even the remotest coastal communities. In a comparatively remote island such as Træna investors tap into emerging economies in tourism, land-based aquaculture, and international labour to support more conventional modes of fish processing.

- There is a concern in both Burgas and Cyprus about the way in which the *local* is increasingly bypassed and marginalised in governance arrangements that privilege the national and the regional. Functions have been rescaled to the meso level, working via regulatory instruments and guidance that make it more difficult to influence and penetrate decision making, especially by local interests. Corruption, hidden corporatist decision making and lack of accountability survive

where governance arrangements are not transparent and are increasingly de-centred from the local.

- However, it would be wrong to see multilevel governance operate in a punitive and extractive way. Åland is an autonomous authority with considerable political and financial autonomy; Údarás na Gaeltachta has significant development powers, capabilities and budgets; and Kunnskapsparken Helgeland mediates more inclusive forms of innovation and development in Træna. The right ‘institutional fix’ for inclusive coastal development is of course, critical for effective empowerment, but forces are often operating in different directions. Local authorities in the Cyprus Lab are being amalgamated, Træna operates as an ‘involuntary small municipality’ and local government in Ireland is weak. The Øy Kommune Prosjektet is a forum bringing the three small island communities in Træna together, which has enabled economies of scale, more effective political lobbying and a strategic approach to local development. Intermediaries can fill the development gap but how they operate and are legitimised in the context of coastal communities matters to the ability of local people to exercise control over decision-making.

Level	Processes	Structure	Transition Coastal Lab
GLOBAL	Coastal locations are exposed to Foreign Direct Investment, speculative (and even predatory) interests. International obligations on fisheries, World Heritage Sites and Ramsar are also spatialized at the local level in a protective way.	The absence of formal structures enables decision making processes to remain obscure, pursue corporatist modes of interest mediation and weak accountability to the wider public and local political representatives.	There is significant investment in the Cyprus, Bulgaria, Ireland and Norway property markets in negative and positive ways but are often manifest in large scale projects, only when the development commences.
EUROPEAN UNION	Natura 2000 protected areas; SACs SPSS; Habitats, Birds, Water Directives, Common Fisheries, LIFE and so on, exert significant downward pressure on local environmental management and planning.	Designations, compliance and land use zonings are captured in a range of statutory policies (environmental) land use designations, spatial planning and spending programmes.	Each TCL has a mix of designation and compliance procedures that set off significant contests in NBS (fishers and environmentalists); industry (tourism and conservation zoning); and extra local bureaucracies and communities.
NATIONAL	The national varies with scale – significant in Ireland and Cyprus in a way that it is not in Norway or Spain.	A growing concern that the national exerts more regulatory, policy and economic authority over the local, mediated via regional authorities, and regulatory mechanisms that often bypass or sideline the local.	Concern in Burgas that the local is hollowed out by an increasing dominant central state agenda. In Ireland, Udaras jump scales to deliver a coordinated local development agenda in Irish speaking areas.
REGIONAL	Rescaling processes see the intermediate, regional and sub-regional as an increasingly important level of decision making.	Formal structures exist including representative assemblies, strong devolved government and coordinating policy mechanisms.	Quasi-independent island authority (F); island nations (C) devolved regional authorities (S); regional assemblies (I) and development intermediaries such as Udaras (I) capable of implementing significant local development programmes.
MUNICIPALITY	Local development plans open formal possibilities for community participation on land/marine use designations, challenging zoning and leveraging political representatives.	Local government, municipalities and clusters of administrative bodies are politically led and enable community access to decision making on planning, development and environmental management.	Statutory local development plans in all the TCL reconcile higher level environmental regulations with local growth objectives.
HYPER-LOCAL	Dynamic local environments with strong community development organisations, NGOs, cooperative businesses and networks active in the development space.	Varying degrees of formality, networks and structures at a community level, but these vary in resources, regulatory power and access to decision making processes.	Church (C) fishers (F,C) sport and language (I, S), community councils and assemblies (C) It is also important to recognise competition within and between place communities in resource-tight environments.

Figure 133 Multilevel governance and community access to decision making.

- As was pointed out in Åland, large-scale corporate fishers cut across local interests, EU environmental policy, local land use designations and the value that fishing has to the intangible heritage of an island community. National constructions of heritage for tourism consumption were rejected in the west of Ireland in favour of more authentic and locally embedded expressions of culture and place. The level at which decisions are made (in different agencies) and how they can be used or resisted is central to the control that communities can exercise over how their lives, past or working heritage are represented.
- There is a vulnerability to organising at the hyperlocal level and a number of TCLs were aware of their dependence on short-term funding and a focus on ‘projects’ rather than systemic change. Tenk Træna was initiated in 2012 in response to the threatened closure of a fishing company, that diversified the economy into algae farming, with the establishment of ‘Bolyst’. Seven people moved into the island as a result of the initiative although the population overall declined, underscoring the need for more ambitious integrated strategies in such circumstances.
- The analysis also noted rescaling processes in which decisions, resources and responsibilities (licencing, marine planning, environmental designations and so on) are relocated to the regional

level. In Norway, 13 municipalities in Helegeland came together to prepare the coastal management plan but integration across functions and inclusion from places such as Træna remained weak. Regional planning guidance have become more prominent in Ireland; and the Autonomous Government of Catalonia have broadened its approach to 'incorporating citizens voices' with e-participation and social media presenting new challenges and opportunities to communities and the voluntary sector.

4. Using the report

This report records and synthesises the work in the six Labs. It serves to raise the cross-cutting issues that will be relevant in thinking about the barriers to development, the challenges that the users of the sea face and how nature is both exploited and a resource for local protection and enjoyment. The aim is that the stakeholder mapping and the policy library will remain useful to each Lab and can be updated and changed as a *living* resource in the development of specific interventions. There are a number of specific applications in the next phase of EmpowerUs including:

Policy alignment: The resource will be especially important in forming and implementing the pilot as each will implicate a range of agencies, programmes and potential partners, depending on its scope and content. Identifying the key policies that can contribute to, promote or learn from the pilot will be important in establishing the rationale for the intervention in each TCL. In this respect the work is tactical by emphasising where policy routines and discourses might work against an intervention; how to avoid it or mitigate its impact; and where and how to deploy particular tactics (and tropes) to challenge objectors and build support for a testable project.

Corporate learning: there is a high degree of convergence across the Labs about the nature of the problems and opportunities each faces and whilst each is unique, the analysis shows how areas might learn from each other. It will be important, in terms of learning, to see how the political, policy, regulatory and institutional system operates in each area and how the pilots address these within a wider European framework. This is especially the case in developing common methodologies to empower coastal communities - does what works in one area operate effectively in another and what then are the implications for EU programmes, institutional cultures, regulatory arrangements and so on. For example, one issue emerging across the TCLs is the importance of social value – wealth is being created by a range of projects (including those supported by the Structural Funds) but what happens to it – does it impact on local people, does it leak out of the area or does it create local multiplier effects. There are implications then about how the EU thinks about designing-in social value criteria to a range of capital and revenue programmes where this is appropriate.

Building alliances to develop and implement the pilot: The analysis has helped to separate out stakeholders in terms of their position, interest in local development, ability to reject proposals as well as those who will be critical partners. When (and as) the pilot is developed, we need to understand how these relate to implementation and practice. For example, some might be *latent* stakeholders who need to be kept satisfied (such as community groups); *apathetic* who can be brought into monitoring arrangements (including the wider public); *defenders* who need to be kept informed (politicians); and *promoters* who should be managed closely (funders, agencies with potential to adopt or scale practices emerging from the pilot). Understanding *who* as well as what is useful and who is not will be important in designing the intervention.

Post pilot impacts: The related issues of scale, replication and adaptation are important as the policy and organisational map helps to identify why, what resources and what agencies might be relevant to building on successful practice. It might also raise agendas, discourses and actors who might be barriers (or even object) to particular proposals. Understanding the politics of scaling is important to plan for at the start of the process.

Evaluating the effects of the pilot: The policy and stakeholder map will also identify evaluation criteria and how the impact of the intervention might be measured. This would include the contribution to key policies and programmes in local development; building skills and community capacities; developing stronger networks; influencing political and resource allocation decisions; creating recognition for an area, problem or solution and so on. This will be determined by the design of the

pilot, but its impact needs to be understood in the context of the wider development of the TCL and in particular the people who live there.

References

- Andreev, S., Grozdanova, E., 1983. Организация и статут на соларите (тузджии) в българските земи под османска власт (Organization and Status of the Solars (Touzdjis) in the Bulgarian Lands under Ottoman Rule). *Българска етнология* 1983/2, pp. 41–52.
- Angus, D., Rintel, S. and Wiles, J., 2013. Making sense of big text: a visual-first approach for analysing text data using Leximancer and Discursis. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 16(3), pp.261-267.
- Bechev, D. (2023) How many elections would it take to end the crisis in Bulgaria?, *Al Jazeera*, 4 April. Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/opinions/2023/4/4/how-many-elections-would-it-take-to-end-the-crisis-in-bulgaria> (Accessed: 24 April 2023).
- BNT Bulgarian National Television 2022. Силна буря се разрази в Бургас, има щети (Strong storm hit Burgas, there are damages), *Bulgarian National Television*, 17 September. Available at: <https://bntnews.bg/news/silna-burya-se-razrazi-v-burgas-ima-shteti-snimki-1207733news.html> (Accessed: 25 April 2023).
- Burgas Land Use Plan 2023. Available at: <https://www.burgas.bg/bg/obsht-ustroystven-plan-na-gr-burgas-s-negovite-kvartali-i-tehnite-zemlishta> (Accessed: 24 April 2023).
- Burgas Regional Administration 2021. Етнокултурни характеристики в населението към 7 септември 2021 г. в Област Бургас (Ethno-cultural characteristics in the population as of 7 September 2021 in the Burgas Region). Available at: <https://www.bs.government.bg/bg/news/view/7/3062> (Accessed: 25 April 2023).
- Burgas Regional Administration, n.d., 'Икономика (Economy) Available at: <https://www.bs.government.bg/bg/index/static/15/> (Accessed: 25 April 2023).
- Cretchley, J., Rooney, D. and Gallois, C., 2010. Mapping a 40-year history with Leximancer: Themes and concepts in the *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 41(3), pp.318-328.
- DFMR, 2014. Long-term Strategic Plan for Aquaculture: 2014-2020. Department for Fisheries and Marine Research, Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment. 18/12/2013 - ТЕЛКО (moa.gov.cy).
- Directorate of Fisheries, (n.d.). Fishermen, fishing vessels and licenses. Available at: <https://www.fiskeridir.no/English/Fisheries/Statistics/Fishermen-fishing-vessels-and-licenses>.
- Fàbrega, E. 2023 "It's not a vacation, it's your life": Privileged identities, ageing experiences, and migration projects of British retirees on the coasts of Spain. Universitat de Barcelona.
- Flatnes, A. and Brastad, B. 2017. Evaluering av Utviklingsprosjekt Træna. Midtveisevaluering. Oxford Research. Available at: <https://oxfordresearch.no/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/Evaluering-av-Utviklingsprosjekt-Traena.pdf>.
- Foley, N., Curtin Bord, R., Mhara, I., Jackson, E., 2016. An Economic Survey to Determine the Level of Seafood Activity and establish its Economic Importance to the Area of Ros an Mhíl.
- Forbord, A. 2022. <https://www.ranablad.no/har-hentet-inn-392-millioner-kroner-i-fersk-egenkapital-for-a-bygge-et-stort-smoltanlegg-onsker-a-rekruttere-ansatte-lokalt/s/5-42-1095085>.
- Frisvoll, S., Storstad, O., Villa, M., Flø, B. E., and Almås, R. 2015. Kommunereformen og øykommuner uten landfast forbindelse. Norsk senter for bygdeforskning. Available at: <https://distriktssenteret.no/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/Kommunerform-og-oykommuner-uten-landfast-forbindelse.pdf>.
- GALP 2023. Xarxa Brava, Confraries. Available at: <https://xarxabrava.cat/portfolio/confraria-de-pescadors-de-cadaques/>.
- Galway County Council, 2022. Galway County Development Plan 2022-2028. Galway.
- Gencheva, B. 2022. Поморийският гигант Sunset Resort затвори. Защо? (The Pomorie giant Sunset Resort closes doors. Why?), *Capital*, 16 December. Available at:

- https://www.capital.bg/biznes/imoti/2022/12/16/4428205_sluchaiat_s_mega_kompleksa_s_unset_resort_koito_zatvori/ (Accessed: 25 April 2023).
- Generalitat de Catalunya 2023. Uses and Management Regulation Plan proposal of the marine area of the Natural Park of Cap de Creus. (Gencat, 2023). <https://participa.gencat.cat/processes/plarectorpncapcreus>.
- Generalitat de Catalunya. 2018. DECREE 118/2018, of June 19, on the governance model of professional fishing in Catalonia. <https://portaljuridic.gencat.cat/eli/es-ct/d/2018/06/19/118>.
- Generalitat de Catalunya 2023. ORDER ACC/46/2023, of March 13, approving the Fisheries Management Plan in Cap de Creus. <https://cido.diba.cat/legislacio/15092243/ordre-acc462023-de-13-de-marc-per-la-qual-saprova-el-pla-de-gestio-de-la-pesca-al-cap-de-creus-departament-daccio-climatica-alimentacio-i-agenda-rural>.
- Gencat 2023. Participació pública per a l'elaboració del Pla Rector d'Ús i Gestió de l'àmbit marí del Parc Natural del Cap de Creus. Barcelona, Spain. Available at: <https://participa.gencat.cat/processes/plarectorpncapcreus>.
- Gencat. (n.d.). Participa en els processos de participació ciutadana. Retrieved from <https://participa.gencat.cat/processes?locale=ca>.
- Gibson-Graham, J.K. & Miller, E. 2015. Economy as Ecological Livelihood, in: Gibson, K., Rose, D.B., Fincher, R. (Eds.), *Manifesto for Living in the Anthropocene*. Punctum Books, pp. 7–16.
- Go to Burgas* 2023. Facebook page. Available at: <https://www.facebook.com/gotoburgas> (Accessed: 27 April 2023).
- Gobierno de España 2023. Plan de gestión de la pesca en el cabo de Creus. Orden ACC/46/2023, de 13 de marzo, por la que se aprueba el Plan de gestión de la pesca en el cabo de Creus (DOG de 16 de marzo de 2023).
- Gómez Mestres, S., & Lloret, J. 2017. The small-scale fisheries guidelines as a tool for marine stewardship: The case of Cap de Creus Marine Protected Area, Spain. In S. Jentof (Ed.), *Small-scale fisheries guidelines. Global implementation. Part 2, Chapter 19: Responsible fisheries and sustainable development. Sustainable resource management.14*, 401-420. MARE Publication Series, with support of FAO organization. Springer Editorial. ISBN 978-3-319-55073-2.
- Gómez, S. 2022. 'The Moral and Ethical Baseline of Marine Socio-Ecological Values: The Case of Recreational and Artisanal Fishing in NW Mediterranean Coastal Waters (Catalonia, Spain)', *Human Ecology*, 50(5), pp. 895–910. doi: 10.1007/s10745-022-00354-0.
- Gómez, S., Carreño, A., & Lloret, J. 2021. Cultural heritage and environmental, ethical values in governance models: Conflicts between recreational fisheries and other maritime users in Mediterranean marine protected areas. *Marine Policy*, 129, 104529.
- Hansson, S., Bergström, U., Bonsdorff, E., Härkönen, T., Jepsen, N., Kautsky, L., Lundström, K., Lunneryd, SG. et al. 2018. Competition for the fish – fish extraction from the Baltic Sea by humans, aquatic mammals and birds. *ICES J. Mar. Sci.* 75: 999–1008.
- Hansson, T., Carey, G. and Kjartansson, R., 2010. A multiple software approach to understanding values. *Journal of Beliefs & Values*, 31(3), pp.283-298.
- Harvey, D., 2006. *Spaces of global capitalism*. Verso.
- Harvey, D. 2010. The right to the city: From capital surplus to accumulation by dispossession. In S. Banerjee-Guha (Ed.) *Accumulation by Dispossession: Transformative Cities in the New Global Order*, Delhi, Sage, pp.17-32.
- Healey, P. 2010. *Making Better Places: The Planning Project in the Twenty-First Century*, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Healey, P., 1990. Policy processes in planning. *Policy and Politics*, 18(2), pp.91-103.
- Horjen, H. W. 2014. Tre dager med festival gir 30 millioner i kassen for øysamfunnet på Træna. E24. Available at: <https://e24.no/naeringsliv/i/JopOIP/tre-dager-med-festival-gir-30-millioner-i-kassen-for-oeyesamfunnet-paa-traena>.

- INE 2022. Cifras oficiales de población de los municipios españoles en aplicación de la Ley de Bases del Régimen Local (Art. 17). Madrid.
- Leipold, S., Feindt, P.H., Winkel, G. and Keller, R., 2019. Discourse analysis of environmental policy revisited: traditions, trends, perspectives. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 21(5), pp.445-463.
- Life for Pomorie 2023. The third year without salt extraction in Lake Pomorie is on the horizon, *Life for Pomorie Lagoon Project*, 15 March. Available at: <https://lifeforpomorielagoon.eu/the-third-year-without-salt-extraction-in-lake-pomorie-is-on-the-horizon-3-157> (Accessed: 24 April 2023).
- Lin, X., Zhang, H., Wu, H. and Cui, D., 2020. Mapping the knowledge development and frontier areas of public risk governance research. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 43, p.101365.
- Lloret, J., Gómez, S., Rocher, M., Carreño, A., & Inglés, E. 2021. The potential benefits of water sports for health and well-being in Marine Protected Areas: A case study in the Mediterranean. *Annals of Leisure Research*. doi: 10.1080/11745398.2021.2015412
- Mediapool 2023. Дюни на "Каваци" продължават да се превръщат в земеделски земи. 14 April. Available at: <https://www.mediapool.bg/dyuni-na-kavatsi-prodalzhavat-da-se-prevrashatat-v-zemedelski-zemi-news346844.html> (Accessed: 27 April 2023).
- Michev, T. et al. 2003. *План за управление на поддържания резерват „Атанасовско езеро“ (Management Plan for the Atanasovsko Lake protected area)*. Sofia: Ministry of the Environment and Waters.
- Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development. 2021. Kyststrategi - Nye jobber langs kysten vil gi vekst og utvikling i Distrikts-Norge. Regjeringen.no. Available at: <https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/2f8acc360e404c8f8f45538c23e5723d/no/pdfs/kyststrategi.pdf>.
- Ministry of Finance, n.d., Structure of Bulgarian Tax System. Available at: <https://www.minfin.bg/en/774> (Accessed: 24 April 2023).
- Mitchell, R.K.; Agle, B.R.; Wood, D.J. 1997. Toward a Theory of Stakeholder Identification and Saliency: Defining the Principle of Who and What Really Counts. *The Academy of Management Review*. 22 (4): 853–86.
- Neumann. 2007. Fiske och fiskeriförvaltning i Ålands skärgård. ÅLÄNSK UTRE DNINGSSERIE 2007:1
- Nikolov, A. 2021. Пет тренда за икономиката на Бургас (Five trends for the Burgas economy), *Capital*, 24 August. Available at: https://www.capital.bg/politika_i_ikonomika/ikonomika/2021/08/24/4217334_pet_trenda_za_ikonomikata_na_burgas/ (Accessed: 25 April 2023).
- Nordiska ministerrådets skärgårdssamarbete. 1993. PEKKA.
- Nordland County Council. 2013. Fylkesplan for Nordland 2013-2025 Regional plan. Nordland fylkeskommune.
- NSI Национален статистически институт (National Statistical Institute) 2021. Население към 31.12.2021 г. по области, общини, местоживее и пол. <https://www.nsi.bg/bg/content/2975/население-по-области-общини-местоживее-и-пол> (Accessed: 25 April 2023).
- NSI Национален статистически институт (National Statistical Institute) 2023. БВП - Производствен метод - национално ниво. Available at: <https://www.nsi.bg/bg/content/2206/бвп-производствен-метод-национално-ниво> (Accessed: 24 April 2023).
- Ó Sabhain, P., McGrath, B., 2020. That’s the boat that reared us. Maritime culture, place and the role of the ‘Galway hooker in southwest Conamara. <https://doi.org/10.1080/04308778.2020.1804161> 58, 77–96.
- Pafi, M., 2021. The Future of Coastal Landscapes: Perceptions and Conflicts on the west coast of Ireland (Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)). Queen’s University Belfast, Belfast.
- Peck, J. 2013. For Polanyian economic geographies, *Environment and Planning A*, 45(7): 1545–1568.

- PIRO План за интегрирано развитие на Община Бургас 2021-2027 г. (Plan for Integrated Development of Burgas Municipality 2021-2027) 2021. Available at: <http://plan.smartburgas.eu/пиро-2021-2027/> (Accessed: 24 April 2023).
- Pi-Sunyer, O. 1977. Two states of technological change in a Catalan fishing community. In M. E. Smith (Ed.), *Those Who Live From the Sea* (pp. 41–56). Saint Paul: West Publishing Co.
- Polanyi, K. 2001 [1944]. *The Great Transformation: The Political and Economic Origins of Our Time*, Boston (MA): Beacon Press.
- Roux, J.P., Fitch-Roy, O., Devine-Wright, P., Ellis, G., 2022. “We could have been leaders”: The rise and fall of offshore wind energy on the political agenda in Ireland. *Energy Res Soc Sci* 92, 102762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ERSS.2022.102762>.
- Rydin, Y. 2003. *Conflict, Consensus, and Rationality in Environmental Planning: An Institutional Discourse Approach*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Rydin, Y. 2007. Re-examining the Role of Knowledge Within Planning Theory. *Planning Theory* 6 (1): 52-58.
- Sandersen, H.T. 2018. Langsomt ble kysten vår egen. Akvakultur, autonomi og avmakt i kommunal kystsoneplanlegging. I: Skorstad, B., Pettersen, E. & Wollan, G. (red.), *Vårt lille land – små samfunn, store utfordringer*. Stamsund: Orkana forlag, s. 219–249.
- Sandersen, H.T., 2021. Interkommunal kystsoneplanlegging på Helgeland. *Kart og Plan*, 114(3-4), 274-290. doi:10.18261/issn.2535-6003-2021-03-04-10.
- Shterionov, S. 1996. Преселнически движения от 30-те години на XIX век и въздействието им върху историческото развитие на Южното българско Черноморие (Emigration movements of the 1830s and their impact on the historic development of the Southern Bulgarian Black Sea coast), in: *Българите в Северното Причерноморие: Изследвания и Материали*. Veliko Turnovo: Veliko Tarnovo University Press, pp. 263–272.
- Smith, A.E. and Humphreys, M.S., 2006. Evaluation of unsupervised semantic mapping of natural language with Leximancer concept mapping. *Behavior Research Methods*, 38, pp.262-279.
- Statistics Norway, (n.d). StatBank. Available at: <https://www.ssb.no/en/statbank>.
- Straube, J. 2019. Lagarbeid-en liten historie om grasrotdemokrati. Available at: <https://airtraena.wordpress.com/2019/07/18/jostraube/>.
- Svels, K., Salmi, P., Mellanoura, J., and Niukko, J. 2019. The impacts of seals and cormorants experienced by Baltic Sea commercial fishers. *Luke Natural resources and bioeconomy studies* 77/2019. <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-326-854-8>.
- Svels, K., Salmi, P., Suuronen, P., Coelho, N.F., Waldo, Å., Königson, S., Lunneryd, S-G., Eriksson, V., Vetemaa, M., Lehtonen, L., Dyrendom Graugaard, N., & Johansson, M. 2022. Mitigating a social conflict between seal, conservation and fisheries in the Baltic Sea: multilevel and synergistic approaches. *TemaNord* 2022:569. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6027/temanord2022-5692>
- Sivén 2021. PEKKA.
- Tilastokeskus. 2022. https://www.stat.fi/til/rakke/2019/rakke_2019_2020-05-27_kat_001_sv.html
- Træna municipality, 2017. Træna 2030. Kommuneplan Samfunnsdel.
- Údarás Na Gaeltachta, 2023. Ros an Mhíl Strategic Enterprise Zone.

Appendices

Annex I In depth interview questionnaire

CONTACT DETAILS

Your name

Organisation

Address

Contact details

ABOUT YOU AND YOUR ORGANISATION

- Could you tell me about your organisation and your role in its work
- What are your organisational aims and is it set down specifically and policy, legislation or programme documents
- Could you outline in more detail the key elements of your work and describe what resources (financial, human capital, physical assets, such as land and buildings; legislative powers) and delivery programmes you use to achieve your organisational aims
- Are there particular projects that your organisation (or group) pursues within the TCL, especially related to the coast and sea

WORKING ACROSS ORGANISATIONS AND SECTORS

We are especially interested in the role of the community and how policies, programmes and businesses impact on them and their quality of life.

- Who do you mainly work with outside your organisation to achieve your objectives?
- It would be useful to identify the key organisations or people who you work with, including the strength and frequency of your contacts and how important they are to achieving your aims and why? Based on the initial stakeholder table these include:
- Organisations, people and networks outside your country such as cross-border institutions, European Union or intergovernmental organisations (IGOs);
- National government; regional authorities;
- Local government (municipality or Council);
- Structures at a community level, such as neighbourhood, village or small town
- The private sector especially business interests in the coastal economy (fishing, tourism, energy, extraction, transport and so on) and key businesses in the supply chain and ancillary sectors;
- Business groups such as Chambers of Commerce, trade associations and industry bodies;
- The community, including local people, community groups, non-governmental organisations, social enterprises, cooperatives and networks.

POLICY SCOPE AND CONTENT

You will have identified the key policies, legislation, programmes, strategy documents and project proposals of the respondent organisation. Can we look at each of these policies and the way in which they are organised and implemented.

For each policy (prioritise key documents evaluated at stage 2 and 3) can you say:

- How the policy was developed, does it have a legislative basis, what research was used to establish priorities?
- Was there public or stakeholder consultations?
- Where was the policy formulated and discussed (what structures such as political institutions at different levels, public inquiries or consultation events);
- Did the policy change over its development;

- What resources are used to implement the policy?
- Who is responsible for delivery?
- Who is targeted/the imagined beneficiary of the policy? Are there anyone who will be disadvantaged because of the policy?
- Do the public, politicians or experts have an opportunity for scrutiny and review?
- How has the policy addressed equality and equity issues including its impact on: religious belief, political opinion, gender, race, migration status, disability, age, marital status, dependants and sexual orientation?
- Has a formal impact assessment been conducted on equality, equity and environmental issues and any mitigation proposed or enacted?

GOVERNANCE AND PARTICIPATION

We are also interested in how your organisation is represented on a range of governmental or governance structures such as partnerships or networks.

- Do you have formal or informal mechanisms to consult or involve the wider public such as, community groups, residents' associations, NGOs, social enterprises, cooperatives and so on?
- Could you say what structures such as local government you participate in?
- Are there other partnerships (sectoral, thematic, including equality categories, such as gender, or area based) where you have representation?
- Do you belong to or lead any networks or informal associations in your policy area?
- How are you represented at a community level, local government, regional bodies and/or national government (although clearly not all will be relevant)?

MONITORING AND EVALUATION

- Do you formally monitor or evaluate the impact for each policy in turn?
- How do you do that methodologically – what type of data do you use (note that any monitoring and evaluation reports should be in the Documents Library)?
- Do monitoring and evaluation processes involve the wider public, politicians, experts or business stakeholders?
- How are results communicated to stakeholders and do they have an opportunity to input into policy development as a result of monitoring?
- Is equality and equity routinely monitored and if so, how?

Annex II List of documents included in the Leximancer discourse analysis

Bulgaria

Governance Level	Document Name	Author / Institution
National	National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria	Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria
Regional	Integrated Development Plan of Burgas Municipality, 2021-2027	Municipality of Burgas
Local	Management Plan at the Maintained Reserve 'Atanasovsko Lake'	Ministry of Environment and Water

Cyprus

Governance Level	Document Name	Author / Institution
National	Multi-annual Strategic National Plan for Marine Aquaculture	Department of Fisheries and Marine Research, Republic of Cyprus
Regional	Regional Development Strategy 2014-2020 (EMFF – for fishing / coastal communities) [the Strategy is in the process of being updated for 2023-2027]	Limassol Development Agency (ANELEM)
Local	Moni, Monagrouli, Pentakomo local development plan(s) [the planning zones are currently in the process of being updated] These maps should be read with the Policy Framework for the Protection of rural areas 1996 – 2014 (current)	Department for Town Planning and Housing, Republic of Cyprus
Sub-local	Decree: Creation of MPA at Ayios Georgios Alamanos	Department of Fisheries and Marine Research, Republic of Cyprus

Finland

Governance Level	Document Name	Author / Institution
Regional	A Living Sea: Aquaculture Strategy for Åland 2014-2020	Åland Provincial Government
Regional	Åland Marine Strategy 2014-2020	Åland Provincial Government
Regional	Åland's implementation of Finland's operational programme for the fisheries sector 2014-2020	Åland Provincial Government
Regional	Fishing and Fisheries Management in the Åland Archipelago	Erik Neuman (Report Author)

Ireland

Governance Level	Document Name	Author / Institution
National	Project Ireland 2040 - National Marine Planning Framework	Government of Ireland
Regional	Social Enterprise Development Strategy	Údarás na Gaeltachta

Regional	Flag West Development Plan	Fisheries Local Action Group (FLAG) West
Local	Galway County Development Plan 2022-2028	Galway County Council
Sub-local	Ros an Mhíl – Strategic Enterprise Zone – Masterplan – Executive Summary	Údarás na Gaeltachta

Norway

Governance Level	Document Name	Author / Institution
National	Coastal strategy (kyststrategi)	Government of Norway, Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development
Regional (county)	County master plan for Nordland County 2013-2025 (Fylkesplan for Nordland 2013-2025)	Nordland County Council
Regional (Helgeland)	Coastal plan Helgeland (coastal zone plan with environmental impact assessment) (Kystplan)	Intermunicipal planning cooperation, 11 municipalities
Local	Municipal master plan (Samfunnsplan)	Træna municipality

Spain

Governance Level	Document Name	Author/Institution
Regional (Autonomous Government of Catalonia)	DECREE 118/2018, of 19 June, on the model of governance of professional fishing in Catalonia. <i>DECRET 118/2018, de 19 de juny, sobre el model de governança de la pesca professional a Catalunya.</i>	Generalitat de Catalunya
Regional (Autonomous Government of Catalonia)	Maritime Strategy of Catalonia 2030 <i>Estratègia marítima de Catalunya 2030</i>	Directorate General for Fisheries and Maritime Affairs – DGPAM – Generalitat de Catalunya
Local	Marine scope management and use plan of the Cap de Creus Natural Park* (PRUG) <i>Pla rector d'ús i gestió de l'àmbit marí del Parc Natural de Cap de Creus* (PRUG)</i>	Generalitat de Catalunya
Local	Order ACC/46/2023, of 13 March, approving the Cap de Creus fisheries management plan <i>Ordre ACC/46/2023, de 13 de març, per la qual s'aprova el Pla de gestió de la pesca al cap de Creus</i>	Diari Oficial de la Generalitat de Catalunya

* The Proposal, known as PRUG, is an unfinished plan because it is in a phase of a collective participatory process.

Annex III.II Regional development policies

Theme	Hits
development	3158
municipality	2102
population	1917
fishing	1516
water	466
number	288
fish	254
sea	237
district	164
built	137
Table	124
average	118

Words: 257,617

Theme: development: Concepts: development, areas, area, local, cultural, environment, infrastructure, including, activities, social, support, economic, resources, natural, people, management, quality, heritage, objectives, use, related, level. Hits: 3158

Theme: municipality: Concepts: municipality, Burgas, territory, city, urban, transport, construction, system, project, network, municipal. Hits: 2102

Theme: population: Concepts: population, region, public, services, main, implementation, projects, measures, period, needs, information. Hits: 1917

Annex III.III Local development policies

Theme	Hits
development	2202
support	1715
area	1119
design	704
water	281
significant	160
period	91
Region	88

Words: 174,136

Theme: development: Concepts: development, sustainable, infrastructure, appropriate, including, existing, planning, provision, plan, public, ensure, facilities, policy, quality, accordance, COUNCIL, residential, access, housing Hits: 2202

Theme: support: Concepts: support, county, rural, economic, local, villages, heritage, County, growth, social, important, future, communities, natural, potential, tourism, population, community. Hits: 1715

Theme: areas: Concepts: areas, area, use, following, sites, change, management, land. Hits: 1326

Excludes Finland

Annex III.IV What concepts is *Development* connected with?

National: Development connection

Regional: Development connection

Local: Development connection

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